

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

D2.2

**State of the Art in game jams and
game-making co-creation practices
amongst Cultural Heritage
Institutions, Creative Industries,
Higher Education Institutions and
Youth Citizens**

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 10109505

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Cultural Worlds and Environments

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Colophon

1st Edition 2024

Grant Agreement ID: 101095058

Project DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14654424

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This publication can be viewed online and downloaded as pdf.

Please visit www.epic-we.eu

How to cite this report:

Costa, C., Fernandes, P., Nunes, I., Gonçalves, M., & Fonseca, M. (2024). State-of-the-Art on game jams and game-making co-creation practices amongst Cultural Heritage Institutions, Creative Industries, Higher Education Institutions and Youth Citizens. (Report No. 2). EPIC-WE Horizon Europe Project DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14654424

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EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

Project Number: GA 101095058

Project Acronym: EPIC-WE

Project title: Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments: youth imagining, creating, and exchanging cultural values and heritage through game-making.

D2.2

State of the Art in game jams and game-making co-creation practices amongst Cultural Heritage Institutions, Creative Industries, Higher Education Institutions and Youth Citizens

Technical References

Deliverable title	State of the art in game jams and game-making co-creation practices amongst Cultural Heritage Institutions, Creative Industries, Higher Education Institutions and Youth Citizens – A Systematic Literature Review (SLR)
Document type	Report
Dissemination level ¹	PU
Work package	WP2 – State of the Art and Good Practices
Task	T2.1; T2.2; T2.3
Lead beneficiary	COFAC - Universidade Lusófona (UL)
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	AU ; AUAS; KEA; NISV; CBC;
Authors	Conceição Costa*, Pedro Fernandes*, Inês Nunes*, Maria Gonçalves*, Micaela Fonseca *Universidade Lusófona (UL)
Due date of deliverable	2024/01/31
Actual submission date	2023/12/31
Reviewed by	Kim Holflod (AU), Sabine Niederer (AUAS), Rikke Toft Nørgård (AU)

PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Status
V2.1	2023/01/29	Shared with Coordinator and WP2 partners for revision
V2.2	2024/01/31	Final revised Version

Acronyms and abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AU	AARHUS UNIVERSITY
AUAS	STICHTING HOGECHOOLO VAN AMSTERDAM
CBC	FONDEN CREATIVE BUSINESS CUP
CHI	Cultural Heritage Institutions
CI	Creative Industries
DBR	Design Based-Research
DiGRA	Digital Games Research Association
DGBL	Digital Game-Based Learning
GGJ	Global Game Jam
HCI	Human-Computer Interaction
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
ICR	Inter-Code Reliability
KEA	KEA EUROPEAN AFFAIRS

NISV	STICHTING NEDERLANDS INSTITUUT VOOR BEELD EN GELUID
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
PAR	Participatory Action Research
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
RCT	Randomised Controlled Trial
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SGJ	Serious Game Jams
SLR	Systematic Literature Review
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
UFPE	Universidade Federal de Pernambuco
UL	COOPERATIVA DE FORMACAO E ANIMACAO CULTURAL CRL -Universidade Lusófona
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
VAP	Values at Play
VNA	Verbs, Nouns, and Adjectives
VASE	Value Sensitive Design

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Summary

The present Report (D2.2) is the result of tasks 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 conducted in work package 2 (WP2) - State-of-the-art and Good Practices, being an update of the Report D2.1.

The new data is presented in the following sections: Youth Empowerment, Types of Game Jams, Games from Game Jams, Negative and Positive Aspects of Game Jams, Positive aspects of game-making with youth, and

Theoretical frameworks for Game Jams. The Discussion is also updated.

This report aims to contribute to theoretical and empirical knowledge on game jams and game-making co-creation practices among Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHI), Creative Industries (CI), Higher Education Institutions (HEI), and Youth.

Following the PRISMA 2020 method, a systematic literature review (SLR) was conducted to answer the following research questions: a) Is there, in sources, a conceptualisation of cultural game jam? b) What processes and tools are available and researched in game-making and game jams with youth participation? c) Who are the main stakeholders and participants? d) Are innovation frameworks presented in sources? e) Are values embedded in

game jams? f) What are the positive and negative aspects of game-jams? g)

What tools and resources are used for youth empowerment?

A total of 68 articles were included in the review: 37 articles from the scientific databases and 31 from external sources. For the review, a coding guide was created in a top-down approach, with the participation of all partners involved in WP2 – Task 2.2. The analysis was conducted using NVivo 14 software with no automation.

Methods

Eligibility Criteria

The method of the present study was developed considering the PRISMA 2020 statement guidelines for reporting systematic reviews (Page et al., 2021). Articles had to be peer-reviewed, written in English, and published between February of 2002 and February of 2023. Additional inclusion and exclusion criteria related to the subject of the articles can be found in Table 1. Articles gathered through the scientific databases where the research formula devised by the authors could be used were separated from other sources, hereafter designated as “External Sources”: 1) electronic sources such as games Associations websites, projects, or funded programmes

websites 2) resulted from citation searching, or 3) were suggested as external sources by project partners.

Table 1- List of exclusion criteria used for the review's screening processes.

Exclusion Criteria	Name	Description
Ex.C. 01	Revision by peers	Not peer-reviewed
Ex.C. 02	Publication Date	Published before 02/2002 or after 02/2023
Ex.C. 03	Language	Not available in English
Ex.C. 04	Availability of Full Text	Full text is not available
Ex.C. 05	Document Duplication	Duplicate record
Ex.C. 06	Ongoing	Describes a project that is ongoing
Ex.C. 07	Not Related	Theme is not relevant to the review
Ex.C. 08	No Game Jam	Does not mention game jams
Ex.C. 09	No Game Development	Does not mention game development
Ex.C. 10	No Youth	Focuses on ages below 16 and above 25 years old or does not specify
Ex.C. 11	No Culture	Does not mention cultural themes and/or heritage
Ex.C. 12	No Innovation	Does not expose practices that are explicitly innovative

Information Sources & Search Strategy

For the review, three scientific databases were searched to gather articles: ACM Digital Library (subsequently referred to here as ACM), b-on, and JSTOR. These allowed for the input of the research formula as it was agreed on by the authors. The authors iterated upon the research formula to gather the greatest number of results that could be relevant to the SLR and the EPIC-WE project. It features several of the terms and themes that are prevalent to

the project, aiming to help identify articles that relate to the goals of the SLR.

The following formulas were tested:

- "game jam*" AND ("youth" OR "young" OR "teen*" OR "adolesc*")
AND ("culture" OR "cultural" OR "communit*")
- "game jam*" AND ("youth" OR "young" OR "teen*" OR "adolesc*")
AND ("culture" OR "cultural" OR "communit*" OR **"innovation"**)
- "game jam*" AND ("youth" OR "young" OR "teen*" OR "adolesc*")
AND ("culture" OR "cultural" OR "communit*" OR **"helix framework"**)
- ("game jam*" OR **"game mak*"**) AND ("youth" OR "young" OR "teen*" OR "adolesc*") AND ("culture" OR "cultural" OR "communit*" OR **"innovation"**)

Formula 04 was selected for the SLR as it featured the term “game mak*”, which broadens the results of the formula to include projects related to game-making that may not be game jams. The term “innovation” was included since it led to an increase in results, compared to the “helix framework”, which added no results (hinting at the innovative element of the EPIC-WE project).

Other digital sources used for the SLR, where the search formula defined could not be applied, were: DiGRA, H2020, and Erasmus+ (see Table 2). Additionally, articles referenced in the EPIC-WE project’s proposal were

directly relevant to the SLR and were included as external sources. Lastly, some sources were identified and gathered via partners of the project.

Table 2 - List of all sources for the articles in the review

Scientific Databases	ACM	
	b-on	
	JSTOR	
External Sources	<i>Digital Databases</i>	DiGRA
		H2020
		ERASMUS+
	Partner Suggestions	
Proposal References		

Selection and Data Collection Process

For screening 1, articles were reviewed by two researchers separately through the Rayyan software in blind mode. Then, both reviewers gathered to discuss and reflect on the inclusion or exclusion of articles where they disagreed or at least one of them had doubts about the inclusion of a specific article (for the list of the exclusion criteria, see Table 1). In screening 2, the sources included for full-text reading were imported to NVivo 14 software, where the analysis was conducted. Two researchers created a coding guide for thematic analysis with themes and topics relevant to the SLR research

questions, meaning a top-down approach. The coding guide was reviewed and iterated with the feedback of the EPIC-WE project members.

The accepted articles were coded by four researchers (no automation was used) using complete sentences relevant to any thematic categories and subcategories of the coding guide.

Intercoder Reliability (ICR)

The Intercoder Reliability (ICR) was computed as a preliminary phase of the content analysis for both the first and second screening stages of the review; currently, the second screening has only been completed for the external sources. Cohen's Kappa was adopted as the ICR indicator. For the first collection of articles to be analysed for screening 01, multiple coding was applied to 12% of the records (158 papers and 2 coders), which is above the minimum recommended (O'Connor & Joffe, 2020). The agreement and disagreement rates for each code and the full sample were computed in Rayyan. Cohen's Kappa was then calculated in MS Excel. An average Kappa of 0.74 for the full coding was obtained representing "substantial" correspondence (Landis & Koch, 1977). The average agreement was 95.57%, and the average disagreement of 4.43%. The obtained scores are acceptable and represent "substantial" correspondence (O'Connor & Joffe, 2020).

Similarly, for the second screening phase, a sample featuring 33 articles (100% of external sources) was codified by four separate coders. On NVivo 14, a code comparison query was run for two groups: A and B. Each group included 2 coders. In screening 2, an average Kappa of 0,76 was obtained, indicating “substantial” correspondence (Landis & Koch, 1977). The average agreement was 98.12%, and the average disagreement was 1,88%.

Synthesis methods

To tabulate and visually display the results of individual studies and synthesis, the authors utilised NVivo 14 to select excerpts of the articles and associate them to categories (codes) of the coding guide. The content of each code category was then exported from NVivo 14 and converted into tables and graphics. MS Excel was used. In the case of comparisons among categories (matrix queries), graphics and tables were generated in NVivo 14.

Results

Study selection

The three digital scientific databases returned the following number of articles: 35 (ACM), 1755 (b-on), 7 (JSTOR). b-on providing the largest number of results was expected as it aggregates results from other databases. Upon exporting the search results into reference files of the type ‘.ris’, both the ACM

and b-on databases removed results that they automatically detected as duplicates in their own archives (ACM removed 15 and b-on removed 287). The reference files were then imported into Rayyan program, a tool to facilitate cooperation for systematic literature reviews, to conduct the Screening 1 phase consisting of two reviewers' analysis of the articles' titles and abstracts. Once the reference files for all three digital databases were imported into Rayyan, 127 additional articles were flagged as duplicates across the three databases and from the same database. The authors reviewed these instances, and all cases were confirmed to be duplicates, bringing the total of duplicates detected in the digital databases up to 429. Upon removal of duplicates, 1368 articles from the digital databases were set to be reviewed on Screening 1: 20 from ACM, 1341 from b-on, and 7 from JSTOR.

Regarding External Sources, a total of 112 articles/websites/projects were identified and then registered in an Excel spreadsheet. Then, the authors categorised each source (with their respective link) according to how relevant they were for the EPIC-WE project after an initial screening process – such as Screening 1 performed with the databases. Some duplicates were removed in this category, including articles already present in the results from the searches made in the scientific databases. The total number of duplicates

detected and removed in the External Sources category was 25, leaving 87 items to be analysed in Screening 1 (See Figure 1).

Through Screening 1, a total of 1320 articles (including 4 systematic literature reviews) were removed from the initial batch of 1368 articles gathered from the databases' searches, leaving 48 articles to be gathered. In the external sources category, 53 from the gathered 87 items were removed (including 2 systematic literature reviews), with 34 being accepted (Figure 1).

Exclusion criteria, excluding the systematic literature reviews, identified when reviewing the scientific databases' articles were: No Game Jam (n = 1309), No Youth (n = 918), No Game (n = 666), No Culture (n = 613), No Innovation (n = 523). For the external sources, exclusion criteria were: Not Related (n = 19), No Game Jam (n = 18), No Youth (n = 18), No Culture (n = 13), No Innovation (n = 8), No Game (n = 4), Ongoing project (n = 2).

When searching for the full papers of the accepted articles, all 82 articles were found. This means that screening 2 was conducted on 48 articles from the scientific databases and 34 from the external sources (Figure 1). For the databases, the second screening removed 11 articles, leading to 37 included articles. The exclusion criteria and their number of instances for this group of articles were: Not Related (n = 10), Wrong Format (n = 1). For external sources, 3 articles were removed from a total of 34 items, with a total of 31

being included in the SLR. The exclusion criteria for the 3 articles removed, as well as their number of instances, were as follows: Not Related (n = 2), Ongoing project (n = 1). After completing Screening 2, a total of 68 articles were included in the review: 37 articles from the scientific databases and 31 from the external sources.

Figure 1 - PRISMA 2020 flow diagram: the identification, screening (O1 and O2), and inclusion of all articles – from scientific databases and external sources gathered for the SLR.

Study characteristics in Screening 1

Since our search criteria are January 2022 to February 2023, in Figure 2 the growing number of publications indicates the growing interest in the field. The values for publications in 2022 and 2023 can be explained by publications from 2022 not being available, as well as the ones from the period (only 2 months) of analysis in 2023.

Figure 2- The growing number of publications in 20 years of game jams

In what respects the most frequent journals where sample sources were published, 83% are in the 1st and 2nd quartile of the Scimago ranking (Table 3).

Figure 3 presents the most frequent authors in sources.

Table 3 - Most frequent Journals in the sources gathered for the review.

Journal	Sources in Journal	Scimago rank
Games & Culture	60	Q1
Simulation & Gaming	25	Q2
Sustainability (2071-1050)	17	Q1
Convergence: The Journal of Research into New Media Technologies	15	Q1
International Journal of the History of Sport	12	Q2
Educational Technology Research & Development	12	Q1
Learning, Media & Technology	11	Q1
PLoS ONE	11	Q1
British Journal of Educational Technology	10	Q1
New Media & Society	10	Q1
International Journal of Serious Games	9	Q3
Journal of Gaming & Virtual Worlds	9	Q3

Figure 3 – Most frequent authors in sources

Coding guide for sources analysis in screening 2

The codebook created has been transformed by researchers, since new categories emerged from the data and some categories were suppressed (a

bottom-up approach). In Table 4 the final coding guide for the SLR is presented, with the number of files coded.

Table 4 – Coding guide in this Report with categories in bold being main categories.

Name	Files
Theoretical Frameworks	65
Game-making Processes	42
Innovation Frameworks	14
Problem Space	6
Jam design	38
Jam delivery and Outcomes	13
Follow-on Opportunity	9
Game-making with youth	5
Research	64
Participants	63
Game Jams & Games	45
Stakeholders	45
Cultural Themes	19
Cultural Heritage	10
Regional Culture	9
European Cultural Values	7
Values in games	13
Empowerment	7
Local and Global policies	2

Study characteristics

Studies in External Sources

In Table 5 the Paper/Study goals and methodological approach are presented for external sources. In external sources (websites, project documentation or papers not indexed in scientific databases), guidelines about game jams, game-making processes and frameworks are more common than research about such models and processes. Therefore, in that context, methodological approach means qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods in research, as well as instruments, procedures, or tools and methodologies to operationalise game jams and game making. In the 31 sources analysed, the qualitative method is the most frequently used (n=23); mixed method is mentioned once (n=1), and in some sources (n=8) no research methods are referred.

Of particular interest for EPIC-WE are Serious Game Jams (SGJ), in which a ‘serious’ thematic constraint is added in comparison to events such as the Global Game Jam (GGJ) - that also have a thematic constraint though normally unrelated to the topics approached by SGJs, or more open game jams whose goal is accelerating prototyping such as in academic and industry contexts. In “Study 1”, a **serious game jam operations manual** was developed and evaluated (Aibara et al., 2022). Since in *cultural game jams*, an appropriation of

cultural heritage by youth participants is crucial, the manual should be critically examined by the EPIC-WE team as a point of departure for the first game jams.

In “study 2”, a serious game jam had two separate sessions (in time), with the first one a thematic workshop and one week later the second one took place for the development of games (Aibara et al., 2022). Learning takes time.

In “studies 3 and 23” the role of serious games in cultural heritage is discussed (Anderson et al., 2010; Mortara et al., 2014). In Kultima et al. (2019), another concept of culture, the Sami indigenous culture, is explored, reflected, and shared through game jamming. This study could be of interest to glocal exchanges in EPIC-WE at the level of the partners’ cultural impact through the EPIC-WE project. Culture, here, has a double meaning: the culture of HEI, CI and CHI and the culture of a European region.

The question of *values in games* or sensitive design is approached in “Studies 5, 6, 8, 14, 15 and 16” with the tools “VASE”, “Grow-A-Game”, a curriculum for “Value Conscious Design”, “The Values Cards” and “The Values at Play

Framework” (Barendregt et al., 2021; Belman et al., 2011; Belman & Flanagan, 2010; Flanagan et al., 2007; Flanagan & Nissenbaum, 2007c).

“Study 4” concerns participants’ learning in Global Game Jam 2012 (GGJ) with the application of mixed methods: a quantitative and qualitative online survey before and after the game jam (Arya et al., 2013).

In “Studies 10 and 7” the *effect* of game jams on developers' sense of community and how to develop games for empathy in players (Salas et al., 2016; Belman & Flanagan, 2010) are respectively analysed. “Study 19” could be of importance for EPIC-WE, in cases where youth participants already know each other prior to the game jams (Goodine & Khaled, 2019).

Kerr & Savage (2019, p. 2) argue that game jams “were strongly shaped by, and in turn contributed to, the wider gender and class imbalance of the local industry and formal games education programmes”. To challenge this, the authors present a procedure for inclusive game-making. They have organised game-making workshops on game design, game writing and game coding. The workshops attracted diverse people, were observed by researchers, and pre- and post- surveys were conducted. Game coding (programming) was revealed to be very labour-intensive for participants’ expectations. While the results of

this study are not presented in detail, the argument about excluding people from game jams is relevant and needs careful thinking from the EPIC-WE team.

Table 5 – Study Goals and Methodological Approach in external sources.

Study	Citation	Title	Paper/Study Goals	Methodological Approach
1	Aibara et al., 2022	Serious Game Jam Operation Manual: Prototype Development and Evaluation	This study proposes a prototype SGJ operation manual.	Qualitative Method: Surveys and interviews.
2	Aibara et al., 2020	Lessons Learned from Serious Game Jams Organized by DiGRA JAPAN	This paper describes the lessons learned from the past seven SGJs, and new approaches used on the 8th SGJ.	Procedure: The serious games jam was divided in two sessions a study session that include a workshop and a development session
3	Anderson et al., 2010	Developing Serious Games for Cultural Heritage: A State-of-the-art Review	The state-of-the-art concerning theories, methods and technologies used in serious heritage games.	Method: Game analysis
4	Arya et al., 2013	An International Study on Learning and Process Choices in the Global Game Jam	Results of an online survey done by Global Game Jam (GGJ) participants in January 2012	Mixed Methods: -Data collected through two online surveys of the 2012 GGJ participants, prior and after to the Jam. The survey included yes or no answers that were attributed to the number 1 and 2 (quantitative) and open questions (qualitative).

5	Barendregt et al., 2021	Teaching for values in design: Creating conditions for students to grow into responsible designers and developers of future technologies	A pedagogical framework called VASE, that offers 28 teaching activities, 12 assessment activities and case descriptions for teaching values in design	Tools: VASE - Pedagogical Framework
6	Belman et al., 2011	Grow-A-Game: A Tool for Values Conscious Design and Analysis of Digital Games	Five case studies about the tool "Grow a Game" cards	Qualitative method: 5 case studies of Grow-a-Game activities.
7	Belman & Flanagan, 2010	Designing Games to Foster Empathy	The use of games to develop empathy in players	Procedure: "We begin with an overview of what scholars have discovered about empathy (..). This is followed by a set of heuristic principles derived from the literature which are intended to have direct and practical applications to the design of games for good."
8	Belman et al., 2009	Instructional Methods and Curricula for "Values Conscious Design"	Instructional Methods for applying values in digital games	Tools: The authors developed a curriculum for "Value Conscious Design"
9	Danilovic et al., 2022	Making Sense of Lived Experiences with Opioid	Digital Game Design as a tool for discussing	Qualitative Research: 20 young adults (18-30) living with opioid

		Addiction through Autobiographical Game Design and Game Jamming Practices	public health (in this case, opioid addiction crisis)	addiction were invited to participate in two weekend-long game jams
10	de Salas et al., 2016	Game Jams as an Opportunity for Industry Development	This paper analyses if game jams have an effect on the sense of community among developers, in this case, in a weak and unsupported development ecosystem.	<p>Qualitative Method:</p> <p>-Online Survey after both Jams.</p> <p>Procedure:</p> <p>There were hosted two game jams within the state of Tasmania:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. TasJam: Voices over the weekend of September 12–13 2015 2. TasJam: Health, was hosted over the weekend of 14–15th of November 2015.
11	ERASMUS + Project, 2023	Game Jams	Gender inequalities in ICT and STEM	NA
12	European Commission, 2020	Gendered innovations 2: how inclusive analysis contributes to research and innovation: policy review	Gender innovation in research	<p>Qualitative Method:</p> <p>-15 case studies</p>
13	Flanagan et al., 2007	A Method For Discovering Values in Digital Games	The “Values Cards” tool as a way to game designers open the discussion on human principles in game design.	<p>Qualitative Method:</p> <p>-2 case studies using “Values Cards” tool.</p>

14	Flanagan & Nissenbaum, 2007-a	A Game Design Methodology to Incorporate Social Activist Themes	This article talks about how to incorporate the social activist themes in games	Qualitative Method: -Survey
15	Flanagan & Nissenbaum, 2007-b	Values at Play: Report on Findings, Publications, Dissemination, and Future Directions	This paper is a report of values at play about the publication, dissemination, and the future directions.	Qualitative Method: -Interviews -Focus groups
16	Flanagan & Nissenbaum, 2007-c	The Values at Play Framework: A (Semi-) Quick Reference	This paper talks about the values at play framework.	Framework: “The Values at Play (VAP) methodology for incorporating values in the context of system design is characterized by three analytically distinct activities: Discovery, Translation, and Verification.”
17	Flanagan et al., 2005	Values at play: Design Tradeoffs in Socially oriented Game Design	Case Study - RAPUNSEL project	Qualitative Method: - Case Study
18	Goddard et al., 2014	Playful Game Jams: Guidelines for Designed Outcomes	This study presents a set of guidelines for jam facilitators to cultivate experiences that support designed outcomes.	Conceptual Paper
19	Goodine & Khaled, 2019	Ctrl+R: Reflections on Prompting Reflective Game Design	“Ctrl+R”, a game design tool used to create new and reflective ideas among game makers	Tool: -Ctrl+R (a game design tool) Qualitative data: -Survey

20	Kerr & Savage, 2019	Spatial Reasoning: Re-Coding Spaces for Inclusive Informal Game Making	How to make Inclusive Informal Game Making	<p>1 Qualitative method:</p> <p>Surveys and observation of three game jams advertised as events for digital and non-digital game makers to ‘collaborate, create, and connect.</p> <p>2. Procedure:</p> <p>The authors ran six informal game making events with the aim of “challenge the language around who can make games, what might constitute a game, and to develop a range of technical and non-technical skills”.</p>
21	Kultima et al., 2019	Sami Game Jam – Learning, Exploring, Reflecting and Sharing Indigenous Culture through Game Jamming	An exploration study about the experiences and lessons learned from Sami Game Jam 2018	<p>Qualitative method:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ethnography approach - Participatory observations
22	Kultima & Alha, 2011	Using the VNA Ideation Game at Global Game Jam	The tool VNA (Verbs, Nouns, and Adjectives) for game-based ideation.	<p>Tools:</p> <p>-VNA was tested as a tool for game-based ideation at the Finnish Game Jam at Tampere (FGJ Tampere) in 2010 and 2011.</p> <p>Method:</p>

				-Randomised controlled trial (RCT)
23	Mortara et al., 2014	Learning cultural heritage by serious games	The state-of-the-art of serious games in the humanities and heritage field and educational objectives of games	Method: Game analysis (focused on cultural awareness, historical reconstruction, and heritage awareness)
24	Olesen & Halskov, 2018	The Dynamic Design Space During a Game Jam	Autobiographical design case study on how design space theory may be used as a theoretical framework that supports the documentation and analysis of a game jam	Theoretical framework: - Based on design space theory Qualitative Method: - Autobiographical case study of a game jam where the author observed and documented the 48-hour game jam where he participated together with a group. Instruments: - Surveys - Interviews - Observation.
25	Plass et al., 2015	Foundations of Game-Based Learning	This article discusses the foundations of game-based learning	Method: Literature Review
26	Raessens, 2006	Playful Identities, or the Ludification of Culture	This article approaches the difference between playful identities and ludification of culture	Qualitative Method: Observation, interviews, discourse analysis and diaries.

27	Ramzan & Reid, 2016	The Importance of Game Jams in Serious games	Game Jams as tool of Science Communication	Qualitative Method: -Case study of the “noPILLS” project
28	Schütz et al., 2019	Co-shaping the Future in Quadruple Helix Innovation Systems: Uncovering Public Preferences toward Participatory Research and Innovation	A tool of innovation in research	Qualitative method: -Interviews “Three-stage model of research 1) Series or workshops in which laypersons produce ideas and objects intended to express their preferences toward technological advances, followed by clustering of their ideas. (2) An expert assessment phase in which engineers estimate when proposed developments may become possible and project these onto technology roadmaps. (3) Before transforming the objects into design prototypes, a public display of the prototypes intended to encourage shared reflection on new and emerging areas of research and technology.”

29	Tait et al., 2019	How can we engage more young people in arts and culture?	This paper is about the difficulty for young people to engage with the offer of arts organizations and propose a framework for overcoming these barriers	Qualitative Method: -Focus group, interviews, workshops, and literature review.
30	Toft & Harrer, 2020	Design Bleed: A Standpoint Methodology for Game Design	“Design Bleed” as an approach to game design	Methodology of game design - Design Bleed “We adopt the term bleed from the live-action role-playing (larp) community, where it refers to a blurring of boundaries between players and characters, such that aspects of the game world spill over into the out-of-game reality or vice versa (Montola 2010; Brown 2014; Bowman 2015). Players and designers interested in bleed pay attention to the quality of relationships between players, levels of trust, personal risks, and room for experimentation (...) Through bleed, distress becomes a source for joyful exploration, providing a “meaningful sense of discomfort” (Jørgensen 2016).

				Qualitative method: - 2 Case studies of the games “Lovebirds” and “Get Your Rocks On”
31	Wirman & Jones, 2019	On The Local Value of Game Jams: Beyond Learning from the Process	This extend abstract, proposes that “there is value in studying also the outcomes of the arguably valuable learning processes that take place at game jams”	NA

Studies in Scientific Databases

In Table 6, the Paper/Study goals and methodological approaches are presented for sources from scientific databases. In the 37 sources analysed the qualitative method is the most frequently used (n=20), quantitative (n=3), mixed methods (n=1) and in some sources (n=4) no research methods are referred. Conceptual papers and critical literature review are also present (n=9).

Since the analysis presented in this report focuses on game-making processes, game jams, culture and CHI, CI, HEI and Youth, a more detailed analysis is presented in the following sections. Studies 42, 49 and 60 are included in Cultural Themes section. In section Types of Game Jams: studies 40, 60, 63 and 65; In section Game Jams and games with societal aims, including with youth participation: studies 32, 34, 44, 45, 48, 50, 51, 52, 53, 56, 61 and 64; in Participants and Stakeholders: studies 33, 35, 52, and 57; in Game-Making

Processes: studies 35, 58 and 62; in Tools: study 62; in Innovation frameworks: 37 and 59.

Both “Study 45”, “Study 46”, and “Study 67” make use of quantitative methodologies. In “Study 45” (Schrier et al., 2021), a series of game jams for youth in Nigerian public schools are made to explore their power and efficacy as practices to stimulate empathy and compassion skills. To assess this, surveys with a Likert scale were used. In “Study 46” (Steinke et al., 2016), to understand the GGJ community and increase the quality of the jams, the authors analyse multiple sources of data, including surveys, using a percentage of agreement. In “Study 67” “exploratory research with a quantitative approach was conducted in order to measure the dependency between participants’ education level and three other variables: source of inspiration, the purpose of the jam and competencies developed in the Global Game Jam (Torres-Toukounmidis et al., 2020).

In what respects the four sources with no methods available: “Study 41” (Musil et al., 2010), “Study 43” (Petri et al., 2018), “Study 47” (Wirman & Jones, 2018), and “Study 52” are short papers conferences from the ACM and B-on databases. It is noteworthy, however, that these studies are not empirical in nature; instead, they are descriptive and rely on existing literature as their foundational basis. The inclusion of these studies is motivated by the anticipation that, despite being

descriptive, they may offer valuable insights and innovative perspectives relevant to the SLR research objectives.

Other studies are not presented in more detail since they are related to categories that will be analysed in Report D2.2, namely processes of learning in game-making or game-based learning, stakeholders' strategies, and local and global policies of importance for EPIC-WE project but directly to informing WP3 and WP4.

Table 6 - Study Goals & Methodological Approach: sources from scientific databases.

Study	Citation	Title	Paper/Study Goals	Methodologic al Approach
32 ACM	Arya et al., 2019	GGJ-Next: The Global Game Jam for Youth	The report discusses the background, curriculum development, event organization, and lessons learned from the GGJ-Next 2018.	Qualitative Analysis: Surveys.
33 ACM	Eberhardt, 2016	No One Way to Jam: Game Jams for Creativity, Learning, Entertainment, and Research	In this article the author argues how game jams have evolved to be not just learning opportunities for participants to sources for innovation and inspiration for sponsors.	Qualitative Analysis: Surveys.
34 ACM	Ferraz & Gama, 2019	A Case Study About Gender Issues in a Game Jam.	The behaviours and environments that either promote or discourage female motivation to participate in game jams	Mixed Method: Qualitative: Case studies, Observation and guided discussions, face-to-face interviews

				Quantitative: Surveys
35 ACM	Freeman et al., 2020	"Pro-Amateur"- Driven Technological Innovation: Participation and Challenges in Indie Game Development	In this paper, an independent indie game development project serves as a case study to investigate the unequal participation in decision-making and the neglect of middle-tier "pro-amateur" end users.	Qualitative Analysis: Interview
36 ACM	Kultima et al., 2016	Building Finnish Game Jam Community through Positive Social Facilitation	This study consists of post-event surveys collected between 2010 and 2016 and statistics collected from the participant registration forms and a picture of the evolution of the Finnish game jamming scene and provide suggestions for national support systems of game industry ecosystems.	Qualitative Analysis: Case study and surveys
37 ACM	Kultima, 2018	Design Values of Game Jam Organizers Case: Global Game Jam 2018 in Finland	This paper presents the findings of a pilot study for game jam organizers' design values.	Qualitative Analysis: Survey
38 ACM	Kultima, 2021	Game Jam Natives?	This paper discusses the conceptualizations of game jams natives capitalising on Marc Prensky "digital natives".	Conceptual paper
39 ACM	Kultima, 2021b	Negative Game Jam Experiences	This short paper explores game jams specifically from the perspective of the negative experiences – exposing what can be	Qualitative Analysis: Surveys.

			missing from the more optimistic views of game jams.	
40 ACM	Lai et al, 2021	Two Decades of Game Jams	This article includes a state of art of two decades of game jams and discusses the different definitions of a game jams.	Qualitative Analysis: Online survey literature review.
41 ACM	Musil et al., 2010	Synthesized Essence: What Game Jams Teach About Prototyping of New Software Products	This paper evaluates the concept of game jam, a community design/development activity, and its positive effects on new software product development with tight schedules in time-oriented, competitive environments.	NA
42 ACM	Nijdam, 2021	Indigenous Worldviews in Digital Games: Sami Perspectives in Gufihtara et al. (2018) and Rievssat (2018)	This paper examines how two digital games produced during the 2018 Sami Game Jam, Gufihtara et al. (2018) and Rievssat (2018), embody and model Sami Indigenous epistemologies.	Qualitative Analysis: Game Analysis
43 ACM	Petri et al., 2018	Pocket Game Jams: a Constructionist Approach at Schools	This paper presents insights into a Pocket Game Jam and gives an outlook on how to use this concept at school.	NA
44 ACM	Preston, 2014	Serious Game Development: Case Study of the 2013 CDC Games for Health Game Jam	This paper describes the use of a large-scale game jam weekend developing 30 games focused on “winnable battles” in the field of public health.	Qualitative Analysis: Focus Group

45 ACM	Schrier et al., 2021	Piloting a Game Jam in Nigeria to Support Empathy and Compassion	This article mentions the development of a game jam focused on identity exploration and perspective-taking for students aged 12 to 20.	Quantitative Analysis: Surveys with a Likert scale.
46 ACM	Steinke et al., 2016	Understanding a community: Observations from the Global Game Jam Survey Data	This article produces and discusses some key observations of game jammers' and uses demographic data and attitudes to verify the different factors that enhance or detract from the jam experience.	Quantitative Analysis: Survey with percentage of agreement.
47 ACM	Wirman & Jones, 2018	Regional Character at a Large-Scale Jam: GGJ Hong Kong 2013-2018	This report gives an overview of the increased number of participants in 6 years of GCJHG and their type of Skills.	NA
48 Jstor	Boom et al., 2020	Teaching through Play: Using Video Games as a Platform to Teach about the Past	The goal of this chapter is to share practical approaches, based on the authors' experiences of how to leverage video games as a tool to teach about the past.	Qualitative Analysis: Case studies
49 Jstor	Young, 2021	Unity Production: Capturing the Everyday Game Maker	This article strategies of companies like Unity Technologies constantly transform and tailor its production platforms to the local norms and practices of everyday game makers to capture a larger market share of the global game industry's creative production sector.	Critical Review

50 b-on	Aurava & Meriläinen, 2022	Expectations and realities: Examining adolescent students' game jam experiences	This article describes the expectations and experiences of young (16- to 19-year-old) digital game jam participants who attend Finnish general upper secondary schools.	Qualitative Analysis: Surveys and interviews.
51 b-on	Balli, 2018	Game Jams to Co-Create Respiratory Health Games Prototypes as Participatory Research Methodology	In this article the author discusses how participatory action research (PAR), and game jams can be mutually enriching activities to achieve social transformation	Literature Review with eleven game jams.
52 b-on	Ciampaglia & Richardson, 2017	The Street Arcade: Creating Social Justice Videogames as a Platform for Community Dialogue	This article mentions the development of a game and platform to promote community dialogue and the sense of justice.	NA
53 b-on	Contreras-Espinosa & Eguia-Gomez, 2022	Game Jams as Valuable Tools for the Development of 21st-Century Skills	This paper summarizes three years of activities designing and studying game jams to develop 21st-century skills, focused on Mexican students aged 12–16 years old	Qualitative Analysis: observation, open-ended questionnaires, and interviews
54 b-on	Copplestone, 2017	But that's not accurate: the differing perceptions of accuracy in cultural-heritage videogames between creators, consumers and critics	This article analyses 156 interviews conducted with videogame industry and cultural-heritage professionals and gamers.	Qualitative Analysis: Interviews.

55 b-on	Denham & Guyotte, 2018	Cultivating critical game makers in digital game-based learning: learning from the arts	This article discusses how art influences the digital game-based learning community (DGBL) in the development of critical makers.	Critical view about the pedagogical approaches of game-based learning.
56 b-on	Dishon & Kafai, 2022	Connected civic gaming: rethinking the role of video games in civic education	This conceptual paper explores existing approaches to the civic role of video games by offering a “connected civic gaming” framework.	Conceptual paper
57 b-on	Egea-Vivancos & Arias-Ferrer, 2021	Principles for the design of a history and heritage game based on the evaluation of immersive virtual reality video games	This paper discusses the specific role of video games in cultural heritage and history teaching is analysed.	Qualitative Method: Questionnaire
58 b-on	Kinnula et al., 2018	‘Worksome but Rewarding’– Stakeholder Perceptions on Value in Collaborative Design Work	In this paper, the authors examine collaborative design projects in school contexts with many different stakeholders.	Qualitative Analysis: Interviews and workshops
59 b-on	Klimas & Czakon, 2022	Gaming innovation ecosystem: actors, roles and co-innovation processes	This study investigates the Polish Gaming Innovation Ecosystem as a globally successful example of a knowledge-intensive and highly creative innovation ecosystem.	Qualitative Analysis: interviews and non-participatory observations

60 b-on	Laiti et al., 2021	Sustaining intangible heritage through video game storytelling - the case of the Sami Game Jam	This article explores how game jams, a rapid collaborative game production format, can work to support the revitalisation of Indigenous self-narratives in the context of Sámi culture.	Qualitative Analysis: participatory observation, interviews, and textual analysis of the games produced during the 5-day long 2018 Sámi Game Jam
61 b-on	Parekh et al., 2021	Board game design: an educational tool for understanding environmental issues	This article reports the findings from an educational board game design workshop based on real world issues for teens aged 13–17 years	Qualitative Analysis: workshop and team discussions (group interview)
62 b-on	Peters et al., 2021	Toolkits, cards and games – a review of analogue tools for collaborative ideation	This article reports a survey of analogue ideation tools within the design and HCI fields, and within commercial practice.	Qualitative Analysis: a three-step literature review and a web search
63 b-on	Saklofske, 2019	Spreadable Jams: Implementing Social Scholarship through Remodelled Game Jam Paradigms	This paper argues that the game jam paradigm, and more generally, what can be effectively adopted, adapted, and repurposed to facilitate a broader social generation and dissemination	Conceptual Paper
64 b-on	Schut, 2007	Strategic Simulations and Our Past: The Bias of Computer Games in the Presentation of History	The article argues the digital game medium that currently tends to result in stereotypically masculine, mechanical, and spatially oriented interactive presentations of history.	Conceptual Paper
65 b-on	Sotamaa et al., 2020	Public Game Funding in the Nordic Region	In this paper, policies related to game industries are explored with focus on the three Nordic countries	Conceptual Paper

			Finland, Norway and Sweden, and investigate what kind of context the Nordic welfare state model has provided for game development.	
66 b-on	Tahir & Wang, 2020	Transforming a Theoretical Framework to Design Cards: LEAGUE Ideation Toolkit for Game-Based Learning Design	This paper describes a ten-step process of transforming the LEAGUE framework into the LEAGUE toolkit (GBL ideation cards), an evaluation of the toolkit with design workshop participants, and design lessons detailing strengths and limitations to support GBL design practices.	Qualitative Method: Workshop, Cards, questionnaire
67 b-on	Torres-Toukourmidis et al., 2020	Global Game Jam in Latin-America, a Collaborative Videogame Learning Experience	This paper explores the development process within the context of the GGJ, calculating the correlation between level of education and source of inspiration, the correlation between level of education and purpose of the game to be designed in the Global Game Jam and the correlation between level of education and skills.	Quantitative Analysis: Chi square, p-values
68 b-on	Young, 2022	Scene Tracing: The Replication and Transformation of Global Industry, Movements, and Genres in Local Game Production	This article explores how the geographical cultural activities of scenes are shifting into virtual environments, and how these virtual spaces are transforming the culture norms and practices of game making and its associated activities, such	Qualitative Analysis: Interview

			as socials, game jams,"talking shop."	
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Cultural Themes

In a total of 68 sources, one can notice that “Cultural themes” are only referred in 19 sources. This gap in research regarding game-making and cultural heritage reflects the relevance and innovation of EPIC-WE (Table 7).

Table 7 – Cultural Themes in Sources.

Name	Files	References
Cultural Themes	19	78
Cultural Heritage	10	55
European Cultural Values	7	9
Regional Culture	9	14

As “Study 29” (Tait et al., 2019) notes, “Although the widespread use of gaming for leisure purposes has been well documented, the use of games to support

cultural heritage purposes, such as historical teaching and learning, or for enhancing museum visits, has been less well considered.” (p.4).

Concerning “European Cultural Values”, the values established by the European Union

(https://european-union.europa.eu/principles-countries-history/principles-and-values/aims-and-values_en) - as outlined in Article 2 of

the Lisbon Treaty (2007) and the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU (2000) - were used as guiding principles. This includes the values of Human

dignity, Freedom, Democracy, Equality, Rule of law and Human rights. In 7 sources, 5 of them dealt with the topic of gender equality and the lack of female

participation not only in game jams but also in the game-making industry. This growing body of research regarding gender reflects the need to integrate these

considerations in the case of game jam practices and organisation, which are relevant to the project EPIC-WE and the European agenda.

Defining “Cultural Heritage”, “Study 23” divides it between tangible cultural heritage, “such as historic sites and buildings, monuments, documents, works of

art, machines, and other artefacts, which are considered worthy of preservation for the future” (Mortara et al., 2014, p. 2), but also anything that relates to

natural environments, such as landscapes, and intangible cultural heritage, that reflects “social values and traditions, customs and practices, philosophical

values and religious beliefs, artistic expression, language and folklore” (p.2). In the relationship between game jams and cultural heritage, “Study 60” (Laiti et

al., 2021), which explores the subject of Sámi heritage, game jams are pointed out as a heritage tool for their growing popularity as a digital collaboration and innovation, but also for their successful use to address social issues, as has been exemplified here. In the study, the 2018 Sami Game Jam successfully produced six cultural games focused on the considerations of Sámi culture, as it is the example of *Rievssat*, which puts the player in the role of a Northern Finnish ptarmigan bird whose habitat that used to provide safety and a home, becomes increasingly dominated by colonising forces, which leaves it uninhabitable and the bird feeling alienated from his birthplace (ibidem). This game is also explored in the context of “Study 42” (Nidjam, 2021) which analyses the indigenous worldviews embedded in two games produced during the 2018 Sami Game Jam, mentioned above.

At last, when considering “Regional Culture”, “Study 6” calls attention to the diversity of values according to the regional culture in which they are inserted. For example, when considering the globalization of the game industry, regional aspects remain a factor of influence in game development: “the regional Nordic game program as well as the Norwegian state has primarily developed policies

to support game development that aims to protect local cultural heritage” (Sotamaa et al., 2020:25).

Values in Games

More focused on the theme of values, “Study 6” (Belman et al., 2011) describes “values conscious design” as when the designers have “systematically considered the moral, social, and political resonances of design features (...)”; these additional constraints to the design lead to the creation of games that are “markedly different than their mainstream counterparts” (p.2). The study highlights games’ ability to facilitate empathetic experiences as the player can inhabit the role of other people in a “uniquely immersive way”. They state that understanding values-conscious design and how to apply it in games has several practical and prosocial applications, helping sensitize people towards important social issues. “Study 15” (Flanagan & Nissenbaum, 2007b), for example, describes the Values at Play (VAP) project that is “dedicated to researching, promoting and supporting the processes through which systems designers can embed humanistic values in their work”. Calling them “games for good”, they list examples of projects such as *Layoff Game* and *Profit Seed* that demonstrate these processes that “teach and inspire social activism, empathy, and other values”. “Study 45” (Schrier et al., 2021) also focuses on the role of games facilitating empathy and compassion skills, with the development of a

game jam focused on identity exploration and perspective among students aged 12 to 20. The jam resulted in two games developed: one called Forgiveness, “which focused on resolving conflicts, understanding that although conflicts can arise, people can learn to forgive others and lend help when they can regardless of the offenses” (Schrier et al., 2021:4) and the other Togetherness, that explored the perspective of rejection and acceptance.

"Study 17" (Flanagan, et al., 2005) and "Study 14" (Flanagan & Nissenbaum, 2007a) present a case study about the Rapunsel project, whose main goal is to alter status-quo perceptions and biases concerning gender gaps in ICT skills and employment access for girls. Still concerning this topic, “Study 34” (Ferraz & Gama, 2019), and "Study 11", an Erasmus+ project still in progress, also focus on the promotion of gender equality, by raising awareness about women succeeding in ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) and STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths). The theme of gender is also explored in “Study 64” (Schut, 2007), which centres on the inner masculine bias existing in the process of game-making. The author notes that in most historical games, for example, there are frequently three common focuses: politics, economics and especially war, with the representation of the military, which, as he explains, “all of these themes are stereotypically male; they fit widely publicized, rough masculine ideals of aggressiveness and domination” (p.222). Most historical or strategic commercial games explore the theme of power

through the association of it with aggression, physical strength, or weapons, where the “good guy” is almost always a “Great White (dead) Men” (ibidem), noting a lack of representativity.

“Study 27” demonstrates how game jams can be used for serious games through the example of the “noPILLS” European research project, which had the long-term aim of “reducing pharmaceutical micro-pollutants in the water cycle” (Ramzan & Reid, 2016). A game jam was used to introduce and tackle this topic in a more dynamic way, leading to the creation of games related to the issue and making it more accessible to a general audience. At last, and considering the relevance of the project, “Study 28” (Schutz et al., 2019) presents the Quadruple Helix Model, a tool for innovation in research and societal advancement.

Youth Empowerment

Youth empowerment, although not having a single and universal conceptualisation, shares among various definitions the recognition of the potential and abilities of young people, providing them with tools, resources, education, and opportunities so that they can actively engage in civic participation. The UNDP (United Nations Development Programme) defines it as “promoting fully inclusive governance, increasing youth participation in decision-making, ramping up youth employment, engaging youth in peacebuilding and gender equality programmes, and ensuring youth are a part

of SDG (Sustainable Development Goals) integration, implementation, and monitoring.” (<https://www.undp.org/governance/youth-empowerment>)

In the context of this research, however, in a total of 53 sources, only seven of them were found relating to “empowerment”, and all of them used the concept with different meanings and contexts, which reinforces the challenge to define youth empowerment, and how should we measure it in research, since both this concepts, individually, have to take in account the historical, social and political contexts they are inserted in.

“Study 58” (Kinnula et al., 2018) employs the concept of empowerment in collaborative design work. The authors use the concept of value co-creation, “where value is understood to emerge from collaborative activity between actors participating in the activity” (p. 463). Here, the focus is on the creation of collaborative design projects in schools involving various stakeholders, leading to the conclusion that “the projects have enabled us to educate and empower the young generation in the issues of participation, design, and technology, and they have allowed us to truly listen to children and incorporate their voices into technology/game design” (p. 479). Thus, the concept of empowerment is associated with providing tools to young people so that they can learn to participate autonomously. In “Study 20” (Kerr & Savage, 2019), which focuses

on the importance of inclusive informal game making, the only reference to “empower” appears in the context of the development of informal learning events. In this study, authors consider that to empower game makers diverse skills and knowledge, it is first necessary to question the socio-cultural norms and the standardized tools used for game development in which game making is inserted.

In “Study 12” (European Commission, 2020), focused on the topic of gender innovation in research, the concept of empowerment is used to concern the importance of “developing technologies and services that empower women to enhance individual capabilities”, but also the relevance of co-creation and co-design to “empower all citizens” to engage in these societal transformations regarding gender.

Another source used this concept referring to youth. Is the case of “Study 29” (Tait et al., 2019), which focuses on the difficulties faced by young people when engaging with arts and culture, where the concept of empower is used to note the importance of philanthropy in saving “young people from missing out on

enjoying art, to ensure they enjoy the benefits of improved confidence and education, and to empower them to tell their stories for us all to hear” (p. 4).

Types of Game Jams

In this review, 21 sources categorise game jams according to their purpose or regional/global affiliation (Table 8). The Global Game Jam (GGJ) is the most frequent in sources (n=14), followed by Indie game jams (n=8), Serious game jams (n=5) and Academia (n=5). Under the EPIC-WE project the category “Game jams in relation to culture” (n=8) was created.

The GGJ, which began in 2009, is the largest and most popular event, taking place worldwide during the same weekend. It is open to students, professionals, and amateurs alike (Aibara et al., 2020; Kultima & Alha, 2011; Arya et al., 2013). Chris Hecker and a group of other game developers/designers captured the philosophy of open, independent game innovation when establishing one of the first game jams in Independent Jam 2002 (Indie) to progress the video game industry (Arya et al., 2013; Goddard et al., 2014; Ramzan & Reid, 2016; Aurava & Sormunen, 2023). In “Study 32” (Arya et al., 2019), the GGJ was adapted to fit the target of youth, with a bigger focus on educational proposes and more oriented to specific learning outcomes, which could attract more partners from schools and governments, and to expand as a tool for teaching educational subjects. In this sense, it’s created the “GGJ-Next Curriculum” that explores the

learning outcomes that should be achieved during the game jam and that focuses on cognitive outcomes (for example, creativity, innovation, problem-solving and logical thinking), skill-based outcomes (for example, focused on the learning of programming, designing and arts in the sense of narrative, audio or visual) and affective outcomes (focused on motivation, confidence, friendship building and networking, but also fun and recreation). After applying this curriculum to the design of a game jam, the authors conclude that adapting the GGJ to younger people can offer a greater environment for learning by focusing on their needs and expectations (ibidem). Serious Game Jam (SGJ) has been organised by DiGRA (Digital Games Research Association) JAPAN every year since 2014 (Aibara et al., 2022), and in tandem with serious games, *social issues* have been approached in themes. In Study 63 (Saklofske, 2019), the concept of Spreadable Jams is discussed as alternative models of open social scholarly research and communication because they integrate the four types of scholarship outlined by Ernest Boyer's *Scholarship Reconsidered* (1990).

In "Game Jams in relation to Culture" no "cultural" game jams were found in sources as a direct tool for EPIC-WE. However, "the game jam is growing to become the culture of game developers, game studying students and researchers" (Aibara et al., 2022, p. 2), and it will have an impact on game-making processes and games as cultural worlds. In Study 40 game jams are a tool for reflection on indigenous cultures, to examine cultural heritage or to

make games at the pace of news cycles - News Jam (Lai et al, 2021). In Study 60 (Laiti et al., 2021) “The production of culture happened in a literal sense, with the ephemeral Sami Game Jam context being formed for the sake of both experimenting with and reflecting on a digital creative process”.

Table 8 - Types of games jams mentioned in sources.

Name	Files	References
Types of game jams	21	82
Global Game Jam	14	28
Indie game jams	8	19
Academia	5	6
Serious Game Jams	5	14
Location game jam	2	4
Moving game jams	1	5
Professional game jams	1	4

Game Jams and games with societal aims

Name	Files	References
Game jams & Games and societal agenda	17	61
For Youth Participation	4	7
Social Issues	16	54

For Youth Participation

Considering “Youth Participation”, in the 68 sources analysed, only four of them referred to “youth participation”, namely “Study 11”, “Study 15”, “Study 48” and

“Study 51”. More specifically, in “Study 11” (ERASMUS + Project, 2023), the lack of methodological approach is noted, with reference only to the four partner schools - Longsands Academy (U.K.), IES Blas de Prado (Spain), 1st General Lyceum of Aigio (Greece), and Constantin Brancusi Technical College (Romania). However, no specific information was provided about recruiting youth participants and their age groups. “Study 11” also focused on the eTwinning approach, which enables students to engage with the project theme and collaboratively generate materials essential for the transnational exchange's advancement. eTwinning is intended for educators/teachers across diverse educational levels, encompassing public and private institutions, school principals, directors of teacher training centres, school librarians, and vocational education instructors.

“Study 15” (Flanagan & Nissenbaum, 2007-b) stated that the team from the “Values at Play” project developed the first reliable framework for understanding how design elements influence the values embedded within software systems, such as games. As products and achievements, “Study 15” introduced the “Vexata Board Game” for middle school kids, whose main goal is to debate and discuss human values in a systematic structure provided via the game format. The curriculum was implemented and assessed within several

USA game design programs at higher education institutions, employing quantitative and qualitative methodologies.

“Study 56” (Dishon & Kafai, 2022), through the development of a connected civic gaming framework, calls attention to the active role youth should have not only as game players but also as game makers, offering them more decision-making power about the games they play and the communities they participate in. In this sense, games are seen here as civic spaces that have the power to simulate youth civic participation. Following this topic, “Study 53” (Contreras-Espinosa & Eguia-Gomez, 2022) also focuses on the power of game jams to serve as a tool for youth to develop the knowledge, skills and roles crucial for them as citizens. The study focuses on Mexican students aged 12-16 years old and includes three years of activities designing and studying game jams centred on these skills.

In “Study 50” (Aurava & Meriläinen, 2022), a qualitative analysis is used to examine the expectations and realities of adolescent students’ attending game jams organized by the authors. The results indicate that the participants valued the creative process of game making, which is directly connected with the desire to learn new skills and make new contacts, the two main motivations identified for attending a game jam. Even though this desire was also accompanied by anxiety and the lack of confidence in skills before attending the event, the authors found that most participants felt that attending the event was positive regarding learning, soft skills, and motivation to try new projects that

involved co-creation or groups, which show that game jams have a potential to be “ice breakers”, and help increase the ability of game-makers to work together. As a way to deal with the stress and insecurities that arise before attending a game jam, the authors suggest doing workshops before the event, focused either on the theme or on learning the basics of digital game making, decreases not only these feelings but also is a good opportunity to fight “the unknown” that comes with working with people: “We have come to the conclusion that when jamming with adolescents without professional skills, as well as first-time jammers, the organisers should choose a software to be used in the game jam beforehand, and teach the basics of that software to the jammers, preferably a couple of days before the jam event.” (Aurava & Meriläinen, 2022:4415). Even though the workshop isn’t made to socialize, it is the first time the jammers connect with each other.

Social Issues

In a total of 68 sources, 16 of them referred to “Social Issues”, which indicates the growing relevance of game jams and games as tools to create people’s awareness and reflection on these subjects. In “Study 52” (Ciampaglia and Richardson, 2017), strategies for addressing social justice issues were used, with 12 games produced by teens who experienced some type of social injustice (for example, racial). After the production of the games, a street exhibition called

“Street Arcade” was also part of the strategy as a way to induce dialogue within the community about the topics covered by the games, giving the young people the power to stimulate civic participation: “The project compelled the teens to recognize and actively shape their relationship with their own community through choosing the themes of the art games we co-created and through the face-to-face conversations that they initiated” (Ciampaglia and Richardson, 2017:20). One of the games, called “Can You Serve and Protect?” explored the tensions between the Chicago Police Department and the African American communities it serves, where the player is a white officer. But not only regarding social justice, but game jams have also been used to communicate and learn science, as “Study 61” (Parekh et al., 2021) explores. The article explores how two theories - Systems Thinking and Learning, and Model Building for Learning - can be two positive tools for engaging young people as producers of games related to complex and scientific themes. A workshop was conducted with four participants aged between 13 and 17, during which they developed a board game about water pollution. The authors described the ideation process, where the participants employed Model Building to understand the theme they were working on before designing the game, simplifying it in scientific terms and applying it to the game design itself. They considered how to use the game to disseminate knowledge and explore the phenomenon of water pollution. The theory of Systems Thinking and Learning is evident in the way in which young

participants, in creating the game, first had to understand the concept of pollution as a system, breaking it down into several factors that had different relationships and connections with each other. Only through these two processes could the participants understand the theme enough to translate it into a successful game capable of transferring knowledge.

Participants and Stakeholders

Participants in game jams and game-making processes are referred in 63 sources as students (n=43) and experts (n=43), game developers (n=42), youth, children, and adults (n=29), and researchers (n=18). Only six sources mention teachers as participants in game jams or game-making processes (see Table 9).

Table 9- Participants

Name	Files	References
Participants	63	1821
Experts	43	1234
Game developers	42	191
Game players	2	4
Number of Participants	18	33
Researchers	18	101
Students	43	1234
Teacher	6	7
Youth, children, teens, adolescents, adults...	29	152

Youth/children age	11	15
Youth/children Gender	6	16

The following definition was used with respects to stakeholders in game-making and game jams: an individual, group, or organisation, who may affect, be affected by, or perceive itself to be affected by a decision, activity, or outcome of a project or a programme. Stakeholders are referred by 45 sources, with Higher Education Institutions (HEI) (n=20), Governmental Institutions (n=19) and Creative Industries (CI) (n=18) as the 3 most mentioned.

Table 10 – Stakeholders.

Name	Files	References
Stakeholders	19	80
Associations	5	7
Creative Industries	18	41
Cultural Heritage Institutions	3	4
European Commission	10	57
Governmental Institutions	19	28
Higher Education Institutions	20	43
Parents	15	67
Teachers	10	18
Youth NGOs	1	1
Youth, children, teens, adolescents, adults....	8	11

In Figure 4 a coding matrix with intersections between the category of Participants (from students to researchers) and a selection of Stakeholders codes (from HEI to CHI) is presented by columns. This analysis shows that students are mentioned in initiatives from all stakeholders, with only one common code for CHIs category. In study 52 (Egea-Vivancos & Arias-Ferrer, 2021) the specific role of videogames in cultural heritage and history teaching is analysed. An evaluation of the virtual reality videogame - *El misterio de la Encomienda de Ricote* - (Escribano-Miralles, 2016) used to tour and learn about the history of a 16th-century building (La Encomienda) linked to the Order of Santiago in Ricote (Murcia, Spain), was conducted with a sample of students of the 3rd and 4th of Compulsory Secondary Education (mean age 15.4 years). The results showed that the students in the sample have great interest and motivation to play those types of video games but, “nevertheless, the knowledge they acquired from playing was very confusing and inconsistent” (Egea-Vivancos & Arias-Ferrer, 2021, p. 387).

Participants and stakeholders in the context of game jams play crucial roles in shaping the landscape of game development, particularly within the framework of learning and professional engagement. “Study 33” (Eberhardt, 2016), mentions that for some participants, engaging in game jams transcends the realm of a mere hobby and evolves into a potential profession or a means of

entertaining others. In such cases, the motivations for participation may shift from the intrinsic joy of playfulness and learning to more tangible externalized rewards, such as prize money, awards, and recognition. This highlights the multifaceted nature of participants' goals in game jams.

Figure 4 – intersections between the category of Participants and Stakeholders.

Game-Making Processes

In all 68 sources, 42 mention game-making processes, and game design processes (n = 34) are the most referred, followed by ideation processes (n =

27), and theme introduction or team building (n=5), terminology that is more specific to the game jams are residual (Figure 5).

Figure 5 - Comparison of the codes “game Jams & games” with game-making frameworks code

“Study 9” (Danilovic et al., 2022) reframes digital game design as a sense-making tool and describes the processes consisting of the following steps: ideation, prototyping, narrative design, interaction design, and audiovisual design. Participants of a game jam will progress through these steps while working with the imposed *constraints* that are part of a game jam, such as a narrow timeframe to develop their games. As described by “Study 24” (Olesen & Halskov, 2018), constraints are part of the designers’ resources and can be separated into three types: *intrinsic* - dictated by the materials chosen (ex. hardware or software), *imposed* (external) - stakeholder requirements or a time frame, or *self-imposed*. These constraints and how the designer works with

them influence the design space¹ and the direction of the project. Participants in game jams will be involved in interdisciplinary learning that is realised when students are making their own games while taking part in an event that is defined by teamwork, time limits, and shared end results (Aurava & Sormunen, 2023).

“Study 5” (Barendregt et al., 2021) highlights the importance that *values* can play on both the product of design and the design process itself. When making games in **cultural game jams**, such as in EPIC-WE, it is important that the youth are aware of the design process, what constraints they have and can work with, and how values play a role in the culture-related games they will be making in the project’s game jams. Moreover, designers need to make decisions about potential value conflicts between and within different stakeholders.

According to “Study 4” (Arya et al., 2013), brainstorming and prior skill assessment between team members resulted in higher satisfaction when compared to the use of existing or individual ideas. Brainstorming is also mentioned in “Study 24” (Olesen & Halskov, 2018), where one of the authors, when conducting participatory observation, described the design process

¹ a conceptual space which encompasses the creativity constraints that govern what the outcome of the design process might (and might not) be.

followed by their group in a game jam. At the start of the jam, the group devised a mind map featuring several terms and associations they made with the theme of the jam, including verbs and nouns, also looking at their knowledge of existing games as sources of inspiration. As the team understood more of the design situation they were addressing and reflected on the approaches they could follow, the design space changed, leading to more self-imposed constraints (ex., work with a 2D perspective). This allowed for a clearer direction for the project and a clear shared view for the group which is vital in the context of a game jam. This communication inside the group is an example of the ideation process part of the game design process as it is described in “Study 9” (Danilovic et al., 2022), and employing the VNA (Verbs, Nouns, and Adjectives) ideation game featured in “Study 22” as a tool can be helpful. This tool is meant to accelerate the ideation process, and a variation of such tools, specifically tailored to the jam's theme, was also tested in the Global Game Jam (GGJ). “Study 22” (Kultima & Alha, 2011) reports that the tailored variation of the VNA "seemed to work well with a theme and time-constrained game design process in the context of GGJ". After working through the ideation process, “Study 24” (Olesen & Halskov, 2018) describes the design process as featuring heavy iteration of several elements of the game’s design, stating that sketching and prototyping played a crucial role in the design process. This is supported by “Study 4” (Arya et al., 2013) survey results: the satisfaction of participants with the outcome (the

game) improved if a solid structure featuring prototyping, frequent reviews, and a formal task list were followed.

While articles were found that describe the design or development process followed in specific projects or game jams, very few articles mention explicit frameworks. Nonetheless, the information gathered can be used to inform the creation of new frameworks or toolkits as part of the EPIC-WE project. Three additional articles that are being analysed and may provide interesting information when considering game-making processes are: 1) "‘Worksome but Rewarding’-Stakeholder Perceptions on Value in Collaborative Design Work" – "Study 58" - (Kinnula et al., 2018) in which the authors examine collaborative design projects in school contexts with various stakeholders; 2) "Toolkits, cards and games – a review of analogue tools for collaborative ideation" – "Study 62" - (Peters et al., 2021) that features a survey of analogue ideation tools featured in the design and HCI literature - and commercial practice; and 3) "Transforming a Theoretical Framework to Design Cards: LEAGUE Ideation Toolkit for Game-Based Learning Design" - "Study 66" - (Tahir & Wang, 2020) where the authors describe a ten-step process used to transform a framework into a toolkit related to game-based learning (GBL) - which could prove insightful when exploring the development of frameworks or toolkits for the EPIC-WE project.

Outcomes of Research

Games from Game Jams

Relatively few articles mention and describe specific games that resulted as outcomes from the game jams they discuss or analyse. Unsurprisingly, game jams following the more popular format of 48 hours, or a weekend (ex. Finnish Game Jam in “Study 22”), led to the creation of simpler games when compared to outcomes from events such as the Sami Game Jam, mentioned in study 60, that lasted five days. Nonetheless, the games mentioned on both articles seem to successfully integrate the jams’ themes.

For the Sami Game Jam (related to the Sami culture), conducted in 2018, each group that participated in the jam integrated one Sami representative that would be involved in the design and creation of the game. Study 60 mentions three specific entries from the games that resulted from the jam, which can be found on the ‘itch.io’ platform – along with the other entries for the jam. Two of these entries feature alternative controllers (*Rievssat*, and *Jodus – On the Move*), and the other is played with a virtual reality headset (*Lost Memories*, and *Jodus*). “Study 22”, published in 2011, mentions one of the games that was developed in the Finnish Game Jam (duration of 48 hours) called *Rhythm of the Stars* – accessible on the ‘Kongregate’ platform, which is a 2D rhythm game that follows the jam’s theme of ‘Extinction’. “Study 27” also mentions specific results from the noPILLS Game Jam, which targeted the creation of games that could make the topic of water pollution more accessible and understandable. From the description the article provides, these games also managed to successfully

integrate the topic of the jam into the game; though they were more similar to Finnish Game Jam's entries in terms of complexity (both share the more popular format of 48 hours).

Table 11 - Games from Game Jams.

Study	Citation	Game Jam	Games from Jams	Description of the Games	URL
60	Laiti et al., 2021	Sami Game Jam 2018	Rievssat 3D - Alt.Ctrl	"In Rievssat the player steps in the role of the Northern Finnish ptarmigan bird, flying through a changing landscape by moving their hand across the Leap Motion controls. Additionally, a custom-built pedal is used to gain speed and altitude, helping the bird navigate air currents."	Games mentioned in article: - Rievssat https://zhamul.itch.io/rievssat
			Lost Memories 3D VR	"Lost Memories was created based on the themes of 'Living outside Samiland' and the titular 'Lost Memories'. The game uses VR, taking the players into a 3D representation of two different worlds. (...) the game imposes the request to make a 'forever choice', simulating the pressure on Sámi community members to determine their lives as either traditional or progressive."	- Lost Memories https://horatiuromantic.itch.io/lost-memories - Jodus - On the Move https://tattz.itch.io/jodus-on-the-move

			Jodus - On the Move 2D Top-Down - Alt.Ctrl	The player stands on a balancing board using wood and felt provided by the Utsjoki Sámi school. Similarly, to Lost Memories, the landscape is divided in two: One part of the screen displays an urban environment, featuring architecture, city infrastructure in grey tones. The other part contains nature elements such as trees, rocks, and a river."	Links to mentioned game jam and its entries on itch.io: - Sami GameJam (2018) https://itch.io/jam/sami-game-jam https://itch.io/jam/sami-game-jam/entries
22	Kultima & Alha, 2011	Finnish Game Jam (GGJ) 2010-2011	Rhythm of the Stars 2D - rhythm game (2011)	"Rhythm of the Stars is a rhythm-based game where you save stars by flying in space and activating your area of effect power. Click to the beat when the diminishing circles hit the edges of your ship. Hit big groups of stars with your star saviour power for big score."	Link to the page of one of the articles mentioned in the article: - Rhythm of the Stars https://www.kongregate.com/games/pekujarhythm-of-the-

			Sexquake (2011)	N/A	stars Links to the mentioned game jam and its entries: https://finnishgamejam2011.wordpress.com/ https://finnishgamejam2011.wordpress.com/games-2011/
27	Ramzan & Reid, 2016	noPILLS Game Jam 2014	Sewer Sweeper 3D - first-person rail shooter	"Sewer Sweeper focuses on water filtration from a first-person perspective. Players shoot at particles representative of micropollutant elements as they move continuously through the pipe environment."	No link to the entries of the games was found. Only a video of Sewer Sweeper's gameplay on YouTube and one of Purity's developer's portfolio pages mentioning the game.
			Polluted 2D - sidescroller	"In Polluted, players learn that the fish have been exposed to pollution within the waters caused by sewage caused by irresponsible disposal methods of humans. Players must manoeuvre a small fish through the treacherous waters, taking shelter in seaweed to avoid being attacked. They must also avoid capsules within the water, which causes certain camera effects and control manipulation to make the player's objectives more difficulty."	
			Purity 2D - resource management	"Purity is a simulation-based management tool that attempts to educate publics and	

				professionals in the effect of pharmaceutical pollution on the wider environment. Players assume the management of a water treatment plant, reflective of some research partners of noPills"	
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Negative and Positive Aspects of Game Jams

Concerning "Outcomes", in 53 sources analysed, only 10 of them addressed negative aspects of game jams, as opposed to 17 sources that focused on the positive aspects. This contrast may reflect a favourable academic and industrial environment towards the conceptualization and use of game jams as tools for the development of skills related to design, game-making, but also at the social and professional level. Of the 53 sources, only two referred to positive aspects of game-making with youth, a circumstance explained by the lack of studies found - five - that focused on this theme.

When referring to positive aspects of game jams, most studies highlighted the development of collaboration and networking skills, adaptability, and learning within a restricted time frame, as well as the ability for innovation and creativity in game-making. As "Study 34" (Ferraz and Gama, 2019) argues, "Game jams are games enthusiasts' encounters for one obvious goal in common: creating games. But more than that, these meetings work as an important networking environment for building social and professional relationships among

individuals in the area, in addition to generating an ecosystem of support favourable to the game development market." (p.1)

Within the industry, game jams have also been recognized as an effective training for entering the market. "Study 38" (Kultima, 2021) notes that many participants discovered potential job opportunities or clients through game jams, as these events, beyond mere competition, are a good platform to show individuals' abilities to handle time or resource pressures and work collaboratively, both common realities in the industry. This enthusiasm for the social interactions and networking expectations of game jams has contributed to the emergence of what Kultima (2021) calls "superjammers": "Game jam enthusiasts, one of the reasons for their extensive involvement with the community is that they find game jams as great platforms for (opportunistic) learning and social engagement. Jams have had a positive impact on the development and upkeep of the superjammers' professional skills and portfolios" (p.23). Many of this superjammers use game jams as an opportunity to explore new tools and technologies that usually they don't have the time or motivation to do so.

When it comes to team working, this study also concluded that game jams, by allowing small teams, have the potential to train jammers to improve working together, since they have to consider everyone's interests, knowledge and skills, at the same time they find a theme that works for all. In addition to developing

teamwork skills, “Study 10” (de Salas et al., 2016), also suggest that local game jams are a great opportunity for creating familiarity and developing partnerships amongst small community members, who would not have known each other if it wasn’t for the jam. In the study, the authors hosted two game jams - Tasjam: Voices and TasJam: Health - in order to analyse the impact of game jams in creating a sense of community among developers, in this case, in a weak and unsupported development ecosystem, as is the case of Tasmania. The results concluded that 92,5% of participants felt closer to other Tasmanian game developers after the jam.

In “Study 34” (Ferraz and Gama, 2019), a survey concluded that when asked about the main motivation to participate in a game jam, 47.6% (N=42) of the participants highlighted learning, and 33.3% (N=42) emphasized developing portfolios, meeting new people, and networking, reinforcing the educational and preparatory potential of game jams for the industry, as one participant expressed, "I believe that game jams are an open door for the game market" (p.7). In addition, “Study 36” (Kultima et al., 2016) highlights how jammers participate in the game jam for the creative process, and the fun of seeing a game come to life, which, in some cases, were better than what the jammers were

expecting. The reality of actually being able to produce a game in less than two days also increased the confidence in producing games.

Another key characteristic of game jams, highlighted as a positive aspect, is the restricted time frame. As study “38” (Kultima, 2021) observes, for many jammers, the interest in participating in game jams lies in the ability to expand the design and game-making process, a crucial skill in the context of commercial game development, not typically cultivated in traditional educational settings. “Study 4” (Arya et al., 2013) also emphasizes that this flexibility is valuable not only in game development but also as an opportunity for jammers to develop innovative and more efficient methods of organization and brainstorming that align with the time constraints faced.

From an academic perspective, “Study 27” (Ramzan and Reid, 2016) highlights the use of game jams as a research method, noting that “the collaborative nature of game jams affords people the opportunity to work on interdisciplinary projects and rapidly prototype ideas, thereby making it a valid design research method” (p.545).

In contrast, when referring to negative aspects of game jams, the majority of studies highlighted the potential for toxic and unhealthy environments arising from excessive competitiveness, where participants with less experience or skill sometimes feel excluded, the sacrifice of sleep and mental health due to time constraints, as well as the tendency for many games to remain superficial and

be forgotten shortly after the conclusion of the game jam. In "Study 26" (Kultima et al., 2016), a "confrontation" between less competitive and more competitive participants is highlighted, occasionally leading to discomfort and frustration when forming groups. The authors observed that reducing excessive competitiveness led to a lighter atmosphere and a greater sense of community. "Study 39" (Kultima, 2021b) also calls attention for the different levels of ambition in a team, that can lead to communication problems or burnout feelings - "few respondents were explaining how they either did not have skills that would carry the ambition that the team chose ending in social friction or frustrations" (p.56).

While time constraints were identified as a positive aspect of game jams earlier, in "Study 38", Kultima (2021) emphasizes that the new generation, which grew up participating in game jams, may not be prepared to handle long production cycles or deepen their design thinking or work with more time-consuming tools. Moreover, the rush to finish quickly may compromise their ability to innovate and be creative, as this requires a process of uncertainty, time, and resources far superior to rapid prototyping and thinking. This results in a growing environment of impatient developers addicted to the rush of seeing a game idea come to life in a few hours. The negative side of speed is also supported by "Study 40" (Lai et al., 2021), which notes that many outputs from game jams are superficial and lack depth in how they explore reality, posing a challenge for companies to turn

a game from a game jam into a complete product. Feelings of distress caused by time constraints happens also at the organizers level, as explained in “Study 39” (Kultima, 2021b), since the level of responsibilities concentrated in most cases in 48 hours may lead to feelings of exploitation and burnout - in some cases, the game jams organizers don’t have the opportunity to join the jam, since they are forced to deal with all the practical arrangements.

Finally, “Study 18” (Goddard et al., 2014) draws attention to game jams like fab48h, where teams are registered in advance. While this ensures a cohesive team and a good balance of skills, it limits one of the jam's purposes: the development of networking skills and team building with strangers.

Positive aspects of game-making with youth

Concerning positive aspects of game-making with youth, the two studies identified, “Study 6” (Belman et al., 2021) and “Study 13” (Flanagan and Nissenbaum, 2007b) focused on the Values at Play approach, which has the potential to inspire innovation in design. As the authors explain, “this is because values conscious designers explore themes and work with constraints that are typically outside of mainstream, entertainment-focused designers’ concern; therefore, they tend to produce games that are markedly different than their mainstream counterparts” (p.2). “Study 13” highlighted how the use of VAP allowed students to have a critical opinion about assumptions of standard design practice, rejecting clichés, and exploring new approaches, which

reflected in the creation of games considered more novel and expressive than the typical output in “standard design courses” (p.3).

Tools

In (Table 12) tools as outcomes of research can be found, separately, since they are practices evaluated. It is worth noting that in “Study 62” is argued that “of the 76 tools reviewed, fewer than a third (21) were associated with published research” (Peters et al., 2021, p. 18), claiming that such fact is a missed opportunity for dissemination of evidence-based practice, and presents a problem for replicability of research. Thus, designers are left with research on the effectiveness of tools they cannot use. Besides being a missed opportunity for the dissemination of evidence-based practice, it also poses a problem for the replicability of research.

Table 12- Tools as outcome of research.

Study	Title	Citation	Study/Research goals	References
19	Ctrl+R: Reflections on Prompting Reflective Game Design	Goodine & Khaled, 2019	“Ctrl+R”, a game design tool used to create new and reflective ideas among game makers	REFERENCE 2 “The resulting tool, called ctrl+R, presents designers with a series of eight random digital “card” questions that are intended to prompt previously unconsidered creative avenues. (...) This tool was used with eighteen game jammers during GGJ 2019”
1	Serious Game Jam Operation	Aibara et al., 2022	This study proposes a prototype SGJ	REFERENCE 1 “Serious Game Jam (SGJ) is one of the major events organized by DiGRA JAPAN every

	Manual: Prototype Development and Evaluation		operation manual	<p>year since 2014. This study proposes a prototype SGJ operation manual.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 3</p> <p>“In conclusion, future event organizers can use the latest Serious Game Jam operation manual and customize it to fit their event based on factors like whether the event is onsite or online, more days for development day, etc.”</p>
22	Using the VNA Ideation Game at Global Game Jam	Kultima & Alha, 2011	The tool VNA (Verbs, Nouns, and Adjectives) for game-based ideation	<p>REFERENCE 1</p> <p>“Verbs, Nouns and Adjectives (VNA) VNA is a simple brainstorming technique developed as part of the Game Space project (Paavilainen et al. 2009) at the University of Tampere. It has three decks of cards: verbs, nouns, and adjectives. Each of the cards has one word printed on it: this word functions as a stimulus and an inspiration for shared ideas. The words have been collected from both digital and non-digital casual games, as the original purpose was to produce casual game ideas. VNA rapidly produces high-level game ideas and as it offers random and surprising stimuli, it results in ideas that the users might not have otherwise come up with (Paavilainen et al. 2009; Kultima et al. 2008a; Kultima et al. 2008b). VNA was used both in 2010 and 2011.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 2</p> <p>“Extinction” VNA variant For the second GGJ we designed a variant of VNA to fit that year’s theme, “Extinction.” The game consisted of the same game mechanic used in VNA, where the decks of cards are laid on the table and each participant take one card at a time ideating on the shared idea, which means the second and third participants always add to the idea that was initialized by using the one from the deck. The second deck was identical to the “Verbs” deck of VNA. The first and last</p>

				<p>decks were different: The first deck was based on the theme “Extinction” including words, sentences, and quotes or other concepts relating to the extinction in one way or another. These were, for example: “Death”, “Only a handful of individuals survive”, “Extermination”, “Loss”, “Birth”, “Creation”, “Beginning”, “Half of presently existing species may become extinct by 2100.”,</p> <p>The third deck was a deck with figures that we call non-symbols (see Figure 2), since they look like they could be symbols, but are open for interpretation. The reason we wanted to provide three decks was that it seemed to work well in the VNA process, providing fast rounds with different stimuli affecting the ideation process.</p>
6	Grow-A-Game: A Tool for Values Conscious Design and Analysis of Digital Games	(Belman et al., 2011)	Five case studies about the tool “Grow a Game” cards	<p>REFERENCE 1</p> <p>“This paper discusses a tool developed by the Values at Play (VAP) project to facilitate values-conscious design and analysis of digital games. Our tool, called the Grow-A Game cards, has been implemented and assessed in numerous advanced and beginner game design courses.</p> <p>REFERENCE 2</p> <p>“The development and implementation of a curriculum to introduce graduate and undergraduate game design students to “values conscious design” (The curriculum is freely available to download at www.valuesatplay.org; for a detailed overview, see Belman, Flanagan & Nissenbaum, 2009).”</p> <p>REFERENCE 4</p> <p>“A deck of Grow-A-Game cards contains four categories or subsets of cards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Values Cards: Each card lists a value term, e.g. trust, privacy, liberty,

				<p>sustainability.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verb Cards: Each card lists a game-related verb, or mechanic, e.g. leading, building, matching, avoiding, nurturing. • Games Cards: Each card names a familiar game to build upon, or mod, e.g. Hopscotch, Pac-Man (Namco, 1980), Civilization (Meier, 1991), World of Goo (2D Boy, 2008). • Issues Cards: Each card names a problematic social issue, e.g. displacement, global warming, racism, urban sprawl.” <p>REFERENCE 8</p> <p>“Recently, the team iterated version 2.0 of the cards, producing three specialized versions: one intended for use with high-school students, the second for university design courses, and the third for expert designers.”</p>
8	Instructional Methods and Curricula for “Values Conscious Design”	Belman et al., 2009	Instructional Methods for applying values in digital games	<p>REFERENCE 2</p> <p>“After discussing the results of this exercise, they use the Grow-A-Game cards to brainstorm ideas for new games and game “mods”. The new game ideas they develop are meant to intentionally embody particular values, such as justice, tolerance, and equity, through their mechanics and representational aspects.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 3</p> <p>“The Grow-A-Game card-deck is a flexible tool that can be used either to analyse prior play experiences or brainstorm new game ideas. 3 In one subset of the Grow-A-Game card deck, each card represents a particular value, such as justice, tolerance, or equality. The deck includes blank cards for users who wish to include values not currently in the deck.”</p>
15	Values at Play: Report	Flanagan & Nissenbaum,	This paper is a report of	<p>REFERENCE 1</p> <p>Grow a Game Cards – A colourful,</p>

	on Findings, Publications, Dissemination, and Future Directions	2007b	values at play about the publication, dissemination, and the future directions.	professionally produced brainstorming tool being used in top game design programs at major universities, in game design companies, and in high school programs; The second iteration comes in three different sets (Adult Beginner, Teen Beginner, Expert). Thousands of participants since 2007 have brainstormed games using these values-centered tools.
36	Design Values of Game Jam Organizers Case: Global Game Jam 2018 in Finland	Kultima, 2018	This paper presents the findings of a pilot study for game jam organizers' design values.	<p>REFERENCE 1</p> <p>This study is drawing from a geographically focused group of Finnish jam organizers as mediators within the commercially successful Finnish game industry.</p> <p>REFERENCE 2</p> <p>The main reason to organize a game jam (Table 3) was that the organizer had a goal to promote something for the participants: a community, company, product, cause, or something else. (...). Couple of organizers wanted to jam themselves had marked additional reasons for organizing (such as building a brand) and couple also run the jam so that they could jam themselves.</p> <p>REFERENCE 3</p> <p>First, the respondents seemed to Favor (Table 5) values of game development as a challenge, games as fun, usability, as well as experimentation. Furthermore, some participants shared in opinion that it was valuable to act as a players' advocate, be technologically agnostic, build immersive experiences and work on simple designs.</p> <p>REFERENCE 4</p> <p>The respondents perceived Global Game Jam (Table 6) as something that also values development as a challenge, but also team effort, technological agnosticism, open-source ideology and</p>

				experimental design. Furthermore, ethics in development, cultural heritage and diversity were agreed to some degree as values of GGJ by the respondents.
43	Pocket Game Jams: a Constructivist Approach at Schools	Petri et al., 2018	Pocket Code's aim is to enable teenagers to creatively develop and share their own software online. The app is freely available on Google Play.	REFERENCES 3 & 4 Like Scratch, programs in Pocket Code are created by snapping together command bricks. The bricks are arranged in “scripts” which can run in parallel, thereby allowing concurrent execution.
62	Toolkits, cards and games – a review of analogue tools for collaborative ideation	Peters et al., 2021	This article reports a survey of analogue ideation tools within the design and HCI literatures, and within commercial practice.	REFERENCE 3 Of the 21 tools described in the literature, only 14 of these are associated with published evaluations: AT-ONE Service Innovation Tools, LEGO Serious Play, Design with Intent, Developmentally Situated Design Cards, Envisioning Cards, Exertion Cards, Generonimos, Grow-a-Game, Inclusive Design Toolkit, Mixed Reality Game Cards, PLEX Cards, Sound Design in Games, Tangible Interaction Framework Cards, and Tiles IoT Toolkit). The remaining 7 describe theoretical foundations and/or rigorous development processes, but not empirical evaluations of tool efficacy.

Theoretical frameworks for Game Jams

In the coding guide and analysis of sources, the framework for game jams developed by Reid et al. (2020) was used. The game jams process in sources

was analysed following the terminology: *Problem Space*, *Jam Design (Guiding Criteria and Logistics)*, *Jam Delivery and Outcomes* and *Follow-On Opportunity*.

Problem Space

Regarding Problem Space, defined in the framework for game jams developed by Reid et al. (2020) as “the overall intention of the applied game jam” (p. 2), we concluded that not all the studies analysed about game jams referred to this specific dimension. In this sense, table 13 gathers all the studies where the problem space of the jam organized was identified or explicit.

Table 13- Problem Space

Study	Reference	Problem Space
9	Danilovic et al., 2022	A game jam was used to understand the opioid crisis from the perspectives of young adults living with opioid addiction.
10	de Salas et al., 2016	TasJam: Voices The themes of the first jam were “Voices” and “Access”, with the aim to promote thinking about diversity and the importance of everyone having a voice and being heard. TasJam: Health The theme of this second jam was to encourage participants to design a game to achieve a health outcome.
20	Kerr & Savage, 2019	3 game jams ran with the aim to challenge the language around who can make games, what might constitute a game, and to develop a range of technical and non-technical skills.

27	Ramzan & Reid, 2016	The aim of “noPILLS Game Jam” was to produce games that would make a complex scientific and environmental issue understandable and accessible.
32	Arya et al., 2019	The aim of “GGJ-Next” was to run a game jam adjusted to youth needs, in order to have a stronger focus on education and define more explicit learning outcomes.
34	Ferraz & Gama, 2019	“UFPE Game Jam”, held in Brazil, was organized with the purpose of studying behaviours and environments that either promote or discourage female motivation to participate in game jams.
37	Kultima, 2018	“Finnish Game Jam” was founded to make the collaboration between the Finnish sites into a legal entity. Finnish Game Jam started as a one jam collaboration but started to grow towards being an organization that supports game making and game jams in Finland.
43	Petri et al., 2018	The theme of “Pocket Game Jam” was to create a learning game that was related to other student’s subjects.
44	Preston, 2014	“Games for Health Game Jam” was organized with the purpose of producing SGJ’s about health issues.
45	Schrier et al., 2021	“The goal of the game jam was to enhance perspective-taking, identity exploration, and connection to others through the process of design, as well as to encourage students to express themselves through game design”.
60	Laiti et al., 2021	“Sámi Game Jam” was used has a tool for the revitalisation of Indigenous self-narratives in the context of Sámi culture.

Jam Design

Guiding Criteria

For the review, the guiding criteria node was defined, following Reid et al. (2020), as the theme and any supporting materials with which to guide and support participants during the game jam, such as presentations and documentation. Several articles mentioned this information regarding game jams, some providing 'general guidelines' while others referred to specific game jams examined in the studies; the latter are featured in this node. One of the more common mentions made was the implementation of a specific theme for the jam, which would be revealed either before or at the start of the jam (Arya et al., 2019 – “Study 32”). Through this, participants can focus their creativity on that specific topic and no group can prepare too much of the game jam ahead of time (Lai et al., 2021 – “Study 40”).

Regarding activities prior to the game jam, some information tends to be provided to the participants. The Global Game Jam (GGJ) releases videos that, besides introducing the theme for the jam, feature presentations from developers giving a rundown of what the participants will be doing at the game jam (Kultima, 2018 – “Study 37”). In (Arya et al., 2019 – “Study 32”), pre-event workshops and educational activities that should be organized in the weeks prior to the game jam are mentioned as part of its roadmap. Articles that analysed 'serious' game jams - having a theme surrounding topics such as social issues, health, and culture - suggest having stakeholders or specialists of the topic play a more active role on the jam, specifically on the participants' preparation for the event (Preston, 2014 – “Study 44”). The article also mentions that these specialists should be integrated into the actual game jam process as a mid-event presentation where participants would show their project to the stakeholders and gather feedback (with enough time to make corrections). This

proposal arises from the notion that once participants began developing their games - having moved past the design phase - they would focus strictly on development, not looking to have further discourse with the stakeholders of the jam's topic regarding the game's design (ibidem). (Eberhardt, 2016 – “Study 33”) also mentions that workshops and talks are used in some jams to teach participants specific skills relevant to the jams, even mentioning a “Values at Play” workshop used to “both model fast prototyping methods as well as to expand participants’ understandings of what games could be about” (p.2). Kultima et al., (2016 – “Study 36”) adds to this discussion that an inclusive environment during game jam that incentivises networking between participants should be sought out, what she calls social design. (Eberhardt, 2016 – “Study 33”) mentions that to assist in the development of the games, mentors that are familiar with the software tools used as part of the jam help participants use them, as well as more experienced participants are encouraged to mentor each other in the areas they were most familiar with. As observed in (Kultima, 2018 – “Study 37”) e (Kultima et al., 2016 – “Study 36”), game jams may choose to award participants for multiple reasons instead of selecting and rewarding only one game. “Study 37” mentions Global Game Jam’s practice of providing specific challenges or optional design constraints that players can choose to undertake for a chance of being awarded at the category of that specific challenge. “Study 36” provides a different alternative where awards were specifically created to recognize “special achievements in the jam projects” (p.2).

Furthermore (Preston, 2014 – “Study 44”) states that in a serious jam related to health the top five teams - and games were awarded according to Game Design, Playability, Educational Value, and Art/Audio - progressed to the next phase of the event where they had two additional weeks to improve their game before

presenting it at an exhibition in front of an audience. After this event, a final winner game was selected, being given the opportunity to the team to further develop their project with content experts and mentors in a paid internship. This is what it is called Follow-On opportunity phase in Reid et al. (2020) game jam framework.

Logistics

The time is a crucial factor in the logistics of a game jam, shaping the event's dynamics. Game jams in sources exhibit a diverse range of durations: (see TABLE 13) from a 48-hour period, which is still the most prevalent, although as highlighted by “Study 43” (Petri et al., 2018), game jams can be as brief as two hours, emphasizing rapid ideation and execution. In contrast, in “Study 60”, Laiti et al. (2021) emphasize the potential for more extended creative exploration with game jams lasting up to five days. “Study 32” (Arya et al. 2019) further extends this temporal spectrum, delving into week-long game jams, which resulted in more games being produced at the game jams. Furthermore, the research highlighted the meticulous consent procedures employed, with jam site applications reviewed for the experience and ability of organizers to work effectively with children. In “Study 47”, Wirman and Jones (2018) shed light on the logistics of the Global Game Jam in Hong Kong, standing out for its accessibility by being free of charge for participants, and point out that the large number of participants make increased competition among participants, due to unfamiliarity. Notably, logistical success was achieved through the implementation of a 1-minute video presentation, addressing the challenge of limited time for game presentations caused by the site's growing size. This nuanced insight into the Global Game Jam in Hong Kong adds another layer to our understanding of the varied logistics shaping these collaborative events. Additionally, “Study 50” (Aurava & Meriläinen's, 2022), which analysed two

game jams, one in Tampere (November 2018) and the other in Helsinki (December 2019), introduced a different dimension to the discussion: when participants are not the typical students and professionals from games creation, pre-jam preparation in game-making processes and/or tools is of importance, enhancing the overall game jam experience for participants. In conclusion the logistics are very dynamic. Different timeframes, how spaces are used, and workshops all play a role in shaping these collaborative events.

Table 14 - Logistics

Study	Citation	Game Jam	Game jam duration	Locations	Number of Participants	Games created	Other relevant Information
60	Laiti et al., 2021	Sami GameJam 2018	5 days	N/A	N/A	Rievssat	N/A
						Lost Memories	N/A
						Jodus - On the Move	N/A
10	de Salas et al., 2016	TasJam: Voices [themes: voices & access] 2015	48h	Startup Spring festival	60	Article does not mention any specific game from any of the jams. It mentions that 14 games were developed for 'TasJam: Health'	N/A
		TasJam: Health 2015	32h	Startup Spring festival	8		N/A

						specifically	
22	Kultima & Alha, 2011	Finish GameJam (GGJ)	48h	1 location (Finland)	N/A	Rhythm of the Stars (2011)	N/A
		2010-2011				Sexquake (2011)	N/A
27	Ramzan & Reid, 2016	noPILLS Game Jam	48h	N/A	10	Sewer Sweeper	N/A
		(game jam to prototype possible ways to approach the topic of aquatic pollution through games)				Polluted	N/A
		2014				Purity	N/A
32	Arya et al. 2019	First GGJ in 2009	N/A	53	1650	N/A	Activities: Week-long activities for children, mentors, parents. Procedures: Jam site applications reviewed for experience and ability to work with children Global Reach: Extended to 108 countries.
		GGJ in 2018	N/A	803	42,811	8,606	

		First GGJ-Next	One Week	39	800	N/A	
40	Lai et al. 2021	Nordic Game Jam Model	48h	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
43	Petri et al. 2018	Game Jam	2h	N/A	N/A	N/A	<p>“The Nordic Game Jam pioneered idea pitching as a basis for group forming at game jams. In this setup, jammers pitch their ideas at the beginning of the jam, and jammers rally and form teams around the ideas they like the best. Højsted et al. [58] call this the Capitalist Method. Opposed to this is the Socialist Method, which focuses on forming the groups before the game concept is ideated.</p>

							Thus, the main conceptual difference between the Capitalist or the Socialist methods is that the former is idea first, while the latter is group first. Højsted et al. [58]” pag.7
46	Steinke et al. 2016	Global Game Jam	48h	90	N/A		<p>Accessibility: Free of charge for participants.</p> <p>Challenges and Adaptations: Intimacy Concerns: Large jam site in Hong Kong leading to limited intimacy between participants.</p>
47	Wirman & Jones, 2018	Global Game Jam Hong Kong (GGJHK)	48h	N/A	N/A	N/A	<p>Competition: Increased competition due to unfamiliarity among participants Game Presentation Times: Limited time for game presentations due to the site's growing size</p> <p>Logistical Success: Implementation of a 1-minute video presentation</p>

50	Aurava & Meriläinen, 2022	First Game Jam in Tampere (November 2018)	48h (18 hours on-site)	3 school	9 students	N/A	Workshop: A separate two-hour Twine workshop conducted two days prior to the jam Voluntary Workshop: Additional voluntary two-hour workshop before the jam even
		Second Game Jam in Helsinki (December 2019)	48 hours (15 hours on-site)	1 school	16 students	N/A	

Jam Delivery and Outcomes

The value derived from a game jam extends beyond the mere act of participation. A crucial aspect involves the assessment of the game jam's achievement of its intended outcomes, as defined within the Problem Space. This evaluation includes an analysis of the created games and their alignment with the predetermined goals. Furthermore, it extends to gauging the level of engagement exhibited by participants and/or stakeholders throughout the jam.

The delivery of a game jam can take various forms, offering different approaches. It could be characterized by exploratory methods, emphasizing self-direction, disruption, and autonomy in the creative process. Conversely, it might adhere to a structured delivery, attempting to channel development efforts towards specific outcomes defined for the game jam.

One significant aspect of evaluation revolves around the participants' learning experiences, encompassing both the acquisition of new skills and a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Additionally, stakeholders play a crucial role in appreciating and comprehending the game jam process. This dual assessment—of the games created and the overall process—provides valuable insights into the game jam's effectiveness and impact.

Table 15 - Game Jams and Outcomes

Study	Title	Citation	Object of Analysis	Description (from references)
47	Pocket Game Jams: a Constructionist Approach at Schools	Petri et al. 2018	This paper describes how the “No One Left Behind” (NOLB) project plans to integrate this approach into school curriculum using two concepts	REFERENCE 1 “The results showed that it is possible to create a game as a team and within a limited time frame of two hours. The games were executable, presented the general game idea, contained several diversifiers, and concepts for additional levels. All teams were very satisfied with the outcomes of their first Jam, but they mentioned that the time frame of two hours was too short. However, all participants agreed that they could imagine conducting PGJs within a school context (e.g., during a lesson) in the future, but they tagged it as “risky” to use during regular lessons. One solution could be to conduct such jams during a project day. it was Although programming with Pocket Code as a team was a new experience for everyone, they mentioned that very interesting and that it had

				worked smoothly when the tasks were split properly”.
2	Serious Game Jam Operation Manual: Prototype Development and Evaluation	Aibara et al. 2020	This study proposes a prototype SGJ operation manual.	<p>REFERENCE 1</p> <p>Out of the five teams, four were able to complete the development and release the game on the itch.io site (The 8th Serious Game Jam 2019) (Figure 3).</p>
10	Game Jams as an Opportunity for Industry Development	de Salas et al. 2016	This study proposes a prototype SGJ operation manual.	<p>REFERENCE 1</p> <p>“Participants in the jams also indicated that the jam was a safe environment for honing existing, or learning new skills, and as illustrated in Figure 5, both TasJams required the development of many of these skills within the context of the intensive game development environment.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 2</p> <p>“With regards the usefulness of TasJams to identify potential work partners, 14.8% of respondents indicated that immediately after TasJam:Voices they felt that the jam had been moderately or very useful in identifying potential work partners, however 66.6% had indicated TasJam:Health was only useful to some or a small extent as a mechanism for identifying potential work partners (see Figure 11). This may indicate that only one instance of a game jam is not sufficient to allow the identification of potential work partners given the time and activity limitations of participating in a jam.”</p>

				<p>REFERENCE 3 “Interestingly however, immediately after TasJam:Health, 43.3% of participants indicated that the jam had been moderately or very useful in identifying potential work partners, and another 43.3% had indicated Tasjam was only useful to some or a small extent as a mechanism for identifying potential work partners (see Figure 11). Suggesting that repeated exposure to the community through game jams may indeed allow for the identification of potential work partners.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 4 “With regards to familiarity amongst the members of the community, the activity of participating in a game jam allowed participants to gain an awareness of others in the local community, and that when subsequent jams were undertaken, there existed an already developed familiarity amongst participants, which was further built on during the second jam.”</p>
32	Using the VNA Ideation Game at Global Game Jam	Kultima & Alha, 2011	This article is about how well the game-based ideation method Verbs, Nouns, and Adjectives (VNA) and similar approaches fit the constrained game design processes.	<p>REFERENCE 1 “Altogether, 188 ideas were recorded, ideated in groups by 42 people.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 2 “In 2011 at FGJ Tampere, 16 pitches were presented, resulting in 11 games during the weekend. The connection between ideas and finalized games varied partly because the teams were formed after the</p>

			<p>pitches, partly because the teams needed to change the concepts during the development process to make the game work. In 2010, the number of submitted games was 8.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 3 “However, the connection between the pitch and the final game description was clear: The pitch: The quest of the particle. The universe is dying – Life itself is on the verge of extinction. You are the mysterious particle-entity dispensing your energy for dying stars. Rhythm-based: Stars are arranged in a rhythmic pattern which you have to hit on time. Sacrifice yourself for the good of the universe and all known life – or let everything face away? Retroish? (music, visuals). Upbeat, heroic “save the galaxy” music.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 5 “However, the connections between the ideas and games are naturally not straightforward and some connections may also be coincidental or trivial. Only three games can be clearly traced to one idea or the combination of two ideas, and only one of the ideas has stayed almost the same from the ideation to implementation. 7 out of 11 games can be traced to a pitch or the combination of two pitches (see Figure 5).”</p>
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				<p>REFERENCE 6 “150 out of the 188 ideas were marked as interesting by at least 1 researcher; 10 ideas by 5 or more researchers. 32 ideas were marked in the personal top 3, and 43 ideas were stated as incomprehensible by more than 5 of the researchers. Only 2 ideas were interesting to 6 out of 7 researchers, and there were no agreed favourites; the highest ranking was 3 votes from different researchers, and only one idea achieved the 3 votes. In total, there was no clear consensus about the ideas. This is not surprising due to the fact that games are experiential products. Consensus was easier to achieve in ranking ideas based on how well they fit with the theme.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 7 “For example, 125 ideas had a connection with the given theme according to at least one researcher and 26 ideas were labelled as theme-related by all of the researchers.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 8 “In practice it might be difficult to refine the method for more restricted ideation processes or settings other than theme-constrained sessions. As the constraints within the game development processes vary and because there are complex combinations of different constraints, there is</p>
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			<p>an additional challenge for designing tools for such purposes.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 11 “Combined, the different cells of the curriculum compass aim to develop students’ knowledge, skills and attitude on multiple levels so that they can grow into well-rounded, responsible design”.</p> <p>REFERENCE 13 “There is an immediacy effect in the culture of sharing ideas, play testing, and collaboration in an immediate setting. This rapid prototype model has been adopted elsewhere with success in allowing the best ideas to effervesce to the top by embracing the possibility of failure to encourage risk taking and by inducing creativity through constraint (Shodhan et al., 2005).</p> <p>REFERENCE 14 “While the data suggests that technical skills (art, audio, design, programming, etc.) did not increase within the 48-hour period, Table 5 shows that the game jams have a positive perceived effect on their skills. This is most pronounced in the participants’ confidence in developing video games, which is likely the result of having just developed one. It is also clear that participants believe the jams positively affect their group skills, which can be seen in the</p>
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				high ratings to “Understanding or appreciating the different roles in game development process” and “Ability to work in team environments”.
4	Arya et al. 2013	An International Study on Learning and Process Choices in the Global Game Jam	This paper reports the results of an online survey done by Global Game Jam (GGJ) participants in January 2012.	<p>REFERENCE 1 Preston et al., (2012) advocate the use of game jams to nurture innovation, computational and rule-based thinking.</p> <p>REFERENCE 2 There is an immediacy effect in the culture of sharing ideas, play testing, and collaboration in an immediate setting. This rapid prototype model has been adopted elsewhere with success in allowing the best ideas to effervesce to the top by embracing the possibility of failure to encourage risk taking and by inducing creativity through constraint (Shodhan et al., 2005).</p> <p>REFERENCE 3 While the data suggests that technical skills (art, audio, design, programming, etc.) didn't increase within the 48-hour period, Table 5 shows that the game jams have a positive perceived effect on their skills. This is most pronounced in the participants' confidence in developing video games, which is likely the result of having just developed one. It is also clear that participants believe the jams positively affect their group skills, which can be seen in the high ratings to</p>

				<p>“Understanding or appreciating the different roles in game development process” and “Ability to work in team environments”.</p>
27	The Importance of Game Jams in Serious Games	Ramzan & Reid, 2016	<p>The aim of the project was to produce games jams that would make a complex scientific and environmental issue understandable and accessible.</p>	<p>REFERENCE 1 “The research partners involved in the noPILLS project were very satisfied with the games that were created during the jam.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 2 “They were all considered as successful demonstrations of the potential that serious game jams can offer in developing rapid prototypical evidence for research initiatives.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 4 “In a study by Preston et al. game jammers rated the quality of their game to be 3,12 out of 5, while they rated the game jam’s effect on their programming, art and design skills was rated to be 4,14 out of 5 [25].”</p> <p>REFERENCE 5 “The first interview in the beginning of the game jam revolved around how people were setting up workspaces for themselves and what tools and software were to be used. Later interviews during the game jam revolved around conceptual and implementation related design considerations and concerns, how people were testing their work and collaborating.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 6 “The Game Jam Prototype:</p>

			<p>Cobots. The following analysis based on the data collection, identifies four key events which had a particularly transforming effect on the design space. The four key events are: 1) establishing the design space, 2) elaborating the design space, 3) inquiry into gameplay options, and 4) breakdown of movement and gameplay in a digital prototype.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 7 “The four events are not necessarily representative for all game jams but had in this case study particularly transforming effects on the 48-design process. During design processes, such as game jams, the design space is constantly transformed, and other events in other game jams may have greater impact on how a design space is transformed than the four events mentioned here.”</p> <p>REFERENCE 8 “Some of our group discussions revolved around how various elements from already existing games could be used as sources of inspiration. For example, P1 described an existing game to P2, while GD listened in. Afterwards, GD suggested an idea for a game concept. Suggested game ideas based on elements of already existing games were considered, given the group’s limited time frame and skills.”</p>
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24	The Dynamic Design Space During a Game Jam	Olesen & Halskov, 2018	This paper presents an autobiographical design case study demonstrating how design space theory may be used as a theoretical framework that supports the documentation and analysis of a game jam	<p>REFERENCE 2</p> <p>In a study by Preston et al. game jammers rated the quality of their game to be 3,12 out of 5, while they rated the game jam’s effect on their programming, art and design skills was rated to be 4,14 out of 5 [25].</p> <p>REFERENCE 3</p> <p>The first interview in the beginning of the game jam revolved around how people were setting up workspaces for themselves and what tools and software were to be used. Later interviews during the game jam revolved around conceptual and implementation related design considerations and concerns, how people were testing their work and collaborating.</p> <p>REFERENCE 5</p> <p>The following analysis based on the data collection, identifies four key events which had a particularly transforming effect on the design space. The four key events are: 1) establishing the design space, 2) elaborating the design space, 3) inquiry into gameplay options, and 4) breakdown of movement and gameplay in a digital prototype.</p> <p>REFERENCE 6</p> <p>The four events are not necessarily representative for all game jams but had in this case study particularly transforming effects on the 48-design process. During</p>
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				<p>design processes, such as game jams, the design space is constantly transformed, and other events in other game jams may have greater impact on how a design space is transformed than the four events mentioned here.</p> <p>REFERENCE 7</p> <p>Some of our group discussions revolved around how various elements from already existing games could be used as sources of inspiration. For example, P1 described an existing game to P2, while GD listened in. Afterwards, GD suggested an idea for a game concept. Suggested game ideas based on elements of already existing games were considered, given the group's limited time frame and skills.</p>
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Follow-on Opportunity

The analysis has unearthed promising avenues for follow-on opportunities. In “Study 34”, Ferraz and Gama (2019) articulate a forward-looking strategy for the Universidade Federal de Pernambuco (UFPE) Game Jam initiative: to organize a larger UFPE Game Jam edition to expand the scope and impact of the project and to enhance the sample size and data collection, thereby ensuring more accurate and reliable results. Additionally, the proposal to execute game jams in diverse locations is a strategic move to capture insights related to gender issues within various cultural and social contexts. “Study 43”, Petri et al. (2018) highlights the development and potential of Pocket Code, a mobile visual programming language, to empower teenagers in creative software development. The authors emphasize Pocket Code's versatility and its integration into non-computer science classes, such as Spanish, Fine Arts, Music, and Physics.

In “Study 15”, Flanagan and Nissenbaum (2007b) propose significant future directions at the intersection of human values and play. They advocate for the development of game assessment cards to aid designers in evaluating ethical values once digital prototypes are created. Emphasizing the importance of practical application, the authors suggest implementing games designed in workshops to validate ideas and translate conceptual designs into testable forms. Additionally, they express a keen interest in collaborating with MMORPG developers to explore the dynamic and social relationships that games provide. To extend the reach of their ideas, the authors aim to engage with large corporations, seeking to create receptivity to ethical considerations and human values in game design within corporate settings.

Innovation frameworks

While 14 sources in 68 are coded in Innovation frameworks, only 3 sources explicitly refer to it: “Study 5” (Barendregt et al., 2021), “Study 28” (Schütz et al., 2019) and “Study 59” (Klimas & Czakon, 2022) with VASE framework, the Quadruple Helix Model, and Polish Gaming Innovation Ecosystem, respectively. VASE is a pedagogical framework meant for formal Education that offers teaching activities for values in design, assessment activities and case descriptions for teaching values in design. The tools and resources provided by VASE are important to game-making processes but unpractical for short-period learning processes that can occur in workshops and game jams. Nevertheless, since in EPIC-WE some type of learning should occur in what respects cultural heritage and European values, as well as assessment, *value-sensitive design* is recommended as an input for WP3. The Quadruple Helix Model, originally conceptualized by Elias Carayannis and David Campbell, was further adapted by Schütz et al. (2019) and such a model is applied in the EPIC-WE proposal and, therefore, of enormous importance for the project. For Schütz et al. (2019, p. 129) “the four core components of an innovation system - academia, industry, government, and society—are not involved in unidirectional push-pull

relationships, but rather in multi-layered, dynamic, bi-directional interactions”. In the study of Polish Gaming Innovation Ecosystem, authors found “four distinctive roles that actors may play in the co-creation processes, that is: direct value creation, supporting value creation, encouraging entrepreneurship, and leadership” (Klimas & Czakon, 2022, p. 2213) and structured the co-innovation process into five stages: co-discovery, co-development, co-deployment, co-delivery, and co-dissemination.

Local and Global Policies

When talking about global and local policies, only two sources were found, but none of them focused directly on cooperation between stakeholders. “Study 65” (Sotamaa et al., 2020) explores existing policies to support game development in Finland, Norway and Sweden’s game industries, in the context of the welfare state model. The authors conclude that in all three countries, the game industry has a strong connection with cultural and innovation perspectives, with a focus on the promotion of national heritage. Since all three countries are small and don’t have a strong complete game industry, the value of this cultural approach to games is reflected in the growing measures that Nordic welfare state has taken to boost and innovate beyond this reality, assuring a public cultural support scheme for game development: “Historically, an active state policy has been seen as a way to counterweight effects of not being a central node in the international circuits of game production, both from a cultural and market standpoint.” (p.21). This reflects how the development of the game industry, by belonging to the creative industries, is very dependent on the national strategies and incentive policies, or lack of it (e.g. tax incentives, subsidies, industry regulations). For example, in the European context, Nieborg and Kloet (2016, cited in Sotamaa et al., 2020) found that the various national game policy initiatives existing in each country reflects different levels of development in the

game industry that are closely tied to these policies. As “Study 65” showed, a strong welfare model in the Nordic countries, along with the concerning of promoting national heritage, reflects how this “countries are leading in research and development expenditures and game-related public research investments” (Sotamaa et al., 2020:3). In Norway, the funding can cover up to a maximum of 75% of the development costs, or 50% of the marketing costs of a single project (ibidem).

“Study 68” (Young, 2022), which also focuses on a national context, in this case Toronto, uses the concept of “scenes”, defined as the connection of “the spatiality of geography with the temporality of cultural activities and artifacts to understand the role of place in the cultural production of media” (p.2). In the context of the game industry and game developers, the study explores how these geographical places are shifting to a growing virtual environment, and how these virtual spaces are transforming cultural norms and practices of game making: “social media was a dominant feature of TOJam 10 and 11, especially Twitter. Primarily using the hashtag #TOJam, game makers tweeted frequently about both their TOJam and game making experiences. Jammers provided frequent updates on their games-in-progress by providing screen captures of GIF Images of their games, such as game menus, art assets, 3D models, and in-engine game captures.” (p.13)

Discussion

The study results demonstrate that several practices for game-making and game jams are documented, and to a lesser extent their impact was researched, with no study being mentioned by their authors as “good practices”, but *practices, and evidence-based practices.*

While articles were found that describe the design or development process followed in specific projects or game jams, very few articles mention explicit frameworks. Nonetheless, the information gathered can be used to inform the creation of new frameworks or toolkits as part of the EPIC-WE project.

In what respects the question a) Is there, in sources, a conceptualisation of cultural game jam? - the results show that no sources refer to “cultural” game jams in comparison to games in relation to culture and particularly cultural heritage. The topic of gender equality and the lack of female participation not only in game jams but also in the game-making industry was salient. This growing body of research regarding gender reflects the need to integrate these considerations in game jam practices and organisation, which are relevant to the project EPIC-WE and the European agenda. In terms of cultural heritage game jams in sources are presented as a *heritage tool*, such as in the subject of Sámi heritage (Laiti et al., 2021) where game jam is seen as a digital collaboration and innovation and to successfully address social issues.

In terms of question b) what processes and tools are available and researched in game-making and game jams with youth participation? - Serious game jams (SGJs) frameworks and tools are more connected with game jams or playful media jams that the EPIC-WE project aims to conduct than frameworks from Global game jams. The operations manual for SGJs is of importance to EPIC-WE, particularly to jam design (guiding criteria and logistics). VNA tool and Grow-a-game card, among others mentioned in this report, are useful for the ideation process and to facilitate values-conscious design and analysis of digital games respectively. Such tools are of value for EPIC-WE game jams or any type of game jam since they were evaluated.

In this SLR, the theoretical framework for game jams developed by Reid et al. (2020) was used as a category of analysis, with the following sub-categories:

Problem Space, Jam Design (Guiding Criteria and Logistics), Jam Delivery and Outcomes and Follow-On Opportunity. Other terminologies could be used but, in that framework, what emerges after the “game jam”, the *Follow-on Opportunity* is of most importance for Research and Innovation projects, such as EPIC-WE, stating what opportunities could emerge from a game jam for all stakeholders: professional development of games, learning, dissemination and business models for Cis, CHIs and HEIs. The Reid et al. (2020) framework aligns with the iterative nature of DBR and EPIC-WE, for organising lessons taken from each cycle in all or particular phases of the game jam process.

The game jam’s problem space should be clearly stated before defining the game jam’s design and research protocols. While there are lessons to consider from this review, adaptation for the EPIC WE context is mandatory.

In terms of innovation frameworks, as expected, besides the Quadruple Helix Framework, already in use in EPIC-WE, the Polish Gaming Innovation Ecosystem (Klimas & Czakon, 2022) is presented as a globally successful example of a knowledge-intensive and highly creative innovation ecosystem, directly related to the game industry. Since the game industry is a stakeholder in EPIC-WE the GIEs (Gaming innovation Ecosystems) could bring important knowledge to the EPIC-WE innovation ecosystem.

Answering question c) who are the main stakeholders and participants? – the present analysis shows that students are the most referred participants in sources and are mentioned in initiatives mainly organised by HEIs and CIs and at less extent by CHIs.

In terms of stakeholders in game-making processes and game jams, students, experts, and game developers, are the most referred and to a lesser extent youth and children. Researchers are less present and/or mentioned in sources, which means that game jams in the literature are events organized without formal

research, or research that was not fully documented. As (Peters et al., 2021) claim in a review of design tools, such fact is a missed opportunity for dissemination of *evidence-based practice and* impacts replicability of research.

Considering game jams with a societal aim, only four sources referred to “youth participation”. Of particular interest, the study results of Aurava & Meriläinen (2022) indicate that the participants valued in game jams the creative process of game making, which is directly connected with the desire to learn new skills and make new contacts. The authors also found that most participants felt that attending the event was positive regarding learning, soft skills, and motivation to try new projects that involved co-creation or groups.

In relation to the question d) Are innovation frameworks presented in sources?

- In 68 sources, only 3 sources explicitly refer to it: the VASE framework (Barendregt et al., 2021), the Quadruple Helix Model (Schütz et al., 2019) and Polish Gaming Innovation Ecosystem (Klimas & Czakon, 2022). VASE is a pedagogical framework meant for formal Education but unpractical for short period learning processes that can occur in workshops and game jams. The Quadruple Helix Model is applied in the EPIC-WE project, therefore, of enormous importance. For Schütz et al. (2019, p. 129) “the four core components of an innovation system - academia, industry, government, and society - are not involved in unidirectional push-pull relationships, but rather in multi-layered, dynamic, bi-directional interactions”. In the study of Polish Gaming Innovation Ecosystem there are four distinctive roles that actors may play in the co-creation processes, such as: “direct value creation, supporting value creation, encouraging entrepreneurship, and leadership” (Klimas & Czakon, 2022, p. 2213). The co-innovation process comprises five stages: co-discovery, co-development, co-deployment, co-delivery and co-dissemination, what means

that the involved stakeholders in EPIC-WE should work in a shared community of learning.

For the question e) are values embedded in game jams? - (Belman et al., 2011, p. 2) study describe “values conscious design” as when the designers have “systematically considered the moral, social, and political resonances of design features” which leads to the creation of games that are culturally different from the *mainstream* games of global game industry. In (Flanagan & Nissenbaum, 2007b) the Values at Play (VAP) project is presented as a framework that designers can use to embed humanistic values in their work. The authors refer to projects such as *Layoff Game* and *Profit Seed*, that demonstrate processes that inspire and put in practice social activism, empathy, among other values. The theme of gender is explored in a few studies, being of particular relevance the gender bias in videogames making (Schut, 2007). The author remarks how in most historical games, there are frequently three common focuses: politics, economics and especially war, with the representation of the military: “all of these themes are stereotypically male; they fit widely publicized, rough masculine ideals of aggressiveness and domination” (p.222).

In what respects question f) what are the positive and negative aspects of game-jams? - when referring to positive aspects of game jams, studies highlight the development of collaboration and networking skills, adaptability, learning within a restricted time frame, as well as the ability for innovation and creativity in game-making, what is of importance for building social and professional relationships among individuals in the games’ area and the development of the gaming market.

Several studies highlighted the potential for toxic and unhealthy environments arising from excessive competitiveness, where participants with less experience or skill sometimes feel excluded, the sacrifice of sleep and mental health due to

time constraints, as well as the tendency for many games to remain superficial and be forgotten shortly after the conclusion of the game jam (Kultima et al., 2016; Kultima, 2021b).

In relation to question g) what tools and resources are used for youth empowerment? - In the context of this SLR, only seven sources refer to “empowerment”, and all of them used the concept with different meanings and contexts. Such fact, reinforces the challenge to define youth empowerment, and how it can be measured, since all the conceptualisations have to take in account the historical, social and political contexts they are inserted in. For (Kinnula et al., 2018) the concept of empowerment is related to collaborative design work in schools through value co-creation, leading to increased youth participation, meaning *teachers* listening youth voices and incorporate them into game design.

At last, but not the least to answer h) what are the outcomes in research of value for EPIC-WE? – the main outcomes from research in sources, valuable for EPIC-WE are documented in Negative and Positive Aspects of Game Jams, Tools and Games from Game Jams.

As a limitation of the study presented, in a SLR some bias could be expected in sources, as well as in the interpretations made by the authors. Another limitation associated with using external sources in a systematic review is the potential for publication bias. Since systematic reviews aim to synthesize existing evidence on a particular topic comprehensively, they often rely on published studies. However, the time and resource constraints inherent in conducting a systematic review may limit the number of studies included. The review team prioritized certain time periods for inclusion or focus on a subset of relevant studies, potentially overlooking valuable data from other time periods. This *selective*

inclusion may introduce a temporal bias, and the findings may not fully represent the evolution of knowledge on the topic over time.

Besides that, this SLR has value for the other work packages in EPIC-WE and it has value for outcomes such as dissemination at conferences and publications since it reviews game jams processes and tools, participants and stakeholders, culture and values in games.

As future work, to use and adapt the tools and frameworks already researched, and/or to find inspiration from them in *researching* and *organising* game jams is of major importance not only for the game industry but stakeholders at large that aim to use rapid prototyping processes to create products and processes or to improve communication in their eco-systems.

Other Information

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101095058.

Competing interests

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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